

TEACHERS' WORK TASK MOTIVATION, SELF-EFFICACY, AND EFFECTIVENESS: BASIS FOR PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive study examined the connections between work task motivation, self-efficacy, and effectiveness among K-12 teachers in a city in the Philippines. A sample of 426 teachers was drawn from a larger pool of 1,424 Basic Education Teachers using stratified non-proportional allocation sampling during the 2023-2024 school year. Data collection involved a modified questionnaire that evaluated work task motivation, self-efficacy, and effectiveness. The instruments used for data collection were subjected to reliability testing to ensure their accuracy and consistency. Findings indicated that most respondents were female with a Master's degree, teaching in elementary schools with 10 years or less of experience. They demonstrated high motivation in various responsibilities, including class preparation and student evaluation. Respondents also reported strong self-efficacy in executing teaching duties, such as adapting instruction and maintaining discipline, and were effective in subject knowledge, assessment, and communication. Notably, differences in work task motivation and self-efficacy were observed based on sex and years of teaching experience, particularly in tasks related to assessment and class preparation. The study found significant relationships between work tasks motivation, self-efficacy, and teacher effectiveness. Based on these assessments and relationships, a professional development program for Basic Education Teachers in Lipa City is proposed to enhance these key variables, aiming to improve teaching performance and educational outcomes.

Keywords: *professional development program, teacher effectiveness, teacher self-efficacy, work tasks motivation*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a noble profession that is being looked up to by society when it comes to training and educating future generations. This might be true despite issues being faced by teachers in general. Teachers perform duties of shaping the intellectual, social, and emotional dimensions of students, laying the foundation for lifelong learning and success. Across nations and cultures, educators are known for dedication, passion, and commitment to the societal improvement. Being facilitators of knowledge and models to youth, the teaching profession encompasses diverse roles and responsibilities that range from curriculum design, curriculum implementation, instructional delivery to classroom management and student assessment. Teachers have been known to be doing their best when they are effective, though most of times the term is being interchanged with efficiency. To be known as effective, teachers should possess a substantial amount of knowledge of subject matter delivered through pedagogical expertise and a genuine concern for their students' well-being.

One indicator and could also be a correlate of teaching effectiveness is motivation to do the tasks that are relative to the holistic implementation of the curriculum. This could be collectively known as work task motivation (Garcia, 2021). Work tasks motivation, as an emerging area of study, focuses on determining the intrinsic and extrinsic factors that drive teachers to perform their duties with dedication, enthusiasm, and commitment. Research indicates that motivated teachers are more likely to excel in various aspects of their profession, which could include motivations for class preparation, teaching, evaluation of students, administrative tasks, and complementary tasks.

Recent studies suggest that teachers who experience personal fulfillment in their work tend to exhibit higher motivation and effectiveness in their roles. This research highlights the positive correlation between work task motivation and both teacher performance and job satisfaction. Specifically, intrinsically motivated teachers often engage more in class preparation, showcasing enhanced creativity, resourcefulness, and effectiveness in developing instructional materials and lesson plans. Additionally, teachers who feel autonomous and competent are more likely to deliver engaging and impactful lessons, emphasizing the importance of intrinsic motivation in the teaching profession (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

One of the primary roles of teachers is to deliver teaching and learning activities for the learners to experience. Class preparation is a critical task for teachers, involving the meticulous planning and organization of lesson content to ensure effective instruction. This process includes designing lesson plans, selecting appropriate materials, and creating engaging activities that align with curriculum standards. Furthermore, motivated teachers are more proactive in using formative assessment strategies (Hattie, 2019) and demonstrate efficacy in administrative tasks (Bandura, 2019). In terms of complimentary tasks, intrinsic motivation fosters a culture of continuous improvement and collaboration among educators, leading to enhanced student outcomes and school effectiveness (Darling-Hammond, 2020). While teachers' primary tasks are to teach and to monitor student progress and development, it is also imperative for teachers to perform teaching-

related activities. These are sometimes called administrative tasks. Administrative tasks are an integral part of a teacher's responsibilities, encompassing a wide range of activities that support the overall functioning of the school. Administrative tasks are crucial for maintaining the structure and accountability of the educational environment (Ingersoll et al., 2019).

In addition to work tasks motivation, another related concept that significantly influences teachers' effectiveness and job satisfaction is self-efficacy. Self-efficacy refers to teachers' beliefs in their capabilities to organize and execute instructional tasks effectively (Bandura, 1997). Self-efficacy could influence various aspects of teaching, including instruction, adaptation to individual student needs, student motivation, classroom management, collaboration with colleagues and parents, and resilience in the face of change. Teachers with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to approach instructional tasks with confidence and creativity, resulting in more engaging and effective lessons (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). Moreover, self-efficacious teachers demonstrate greater adaptability and flexibility in tailoring instruction to meet the diverse learning needs and preferences of their students (Bandura, 2021).

Self-efficacy is also an indicator to ensure that instructions or teaching and learning activities are adjusted to individual student needs. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to recognize and address diverse learning styles and abilities in their classrooms (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). They feel confident in differentiating instruction and providing appropriate support for students who may need extra help or advanced challenges (Goddard et al., 2020). This adaptability is essential for creating an inclusive learning environment where all students can thrive. Teachers who believe in their ability to meet individual needs are also more persistent in finding effective strategies and interventions; their self-efficacy contributes to better student engagement and achievement, as they can tailor their teaching to ensure every student reaches their full potential.

Furthermore, self-efficacious teachers are adept at motivating students to set high expectations for themselves, persevere in the face of challenges, and take ownership of their learning (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). Additionally, teachers with strong self-efficacy beliefs are better equipped to maintain discipline and create a positive classroom environment conducive to learning (Bandura, 1997). They could demonstrate effective classroom management strategies, establish clear expectations, and provide consistent support and encouragement to their students.

Another dimension of teaching that needs teacher self-efficacy is the area of student discipline. Teachers with high self-efficacy are confident in their ability to establish and enforce clear behavioral expectations and classroom rules (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2020). They are more consistent in applying disciplinary measures and are better at de-escalating conflicts and addressing disruptive behavior. This confidence allows them to create a safe and orderly learning environment where students feel respected and focused on learning (Miller et al., 2021).

Moreover, self-efficacy is closely linked to teachers' ability to collaborate with colleagues and parents effectively. Those teachers who believe in their ability to work collaboratively are more likely to seek support, share resources, and engage in professional dialogue to enhance their practice (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). They also demonstrate greater resilience in coping with change, whether it be curriculum reforms, policy shifts, or technological advancements, by viewing challenges as opportunities for growth and innovation (Bandura, 1997).

To sum of the efficacy of teachers, coping with changes and adapting to new challenges in the educational landscape would help teachers perform their duties and responsibilities. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more resilient and adaptable, able to embrace new technologies, curricula, and teaching methods (Vaughan, 2020). They view changes as opportunities for growth rather than obstacles, which enables them to stay current with educational advancements and improve their teaching practices.

The foregoing discussion elaborated how important teacher self-efficacy is in teaching and in the performance of teaching related duty. The succeeding discussions will also elucidate the importance of teacher self-efficacy and work task motivations and their roles in teacher effectiveness, by shaping teachers' beliefs in their abilities to manage classroom tasks, engage students, and foster a positive learning environment. As previously discussed, effective teachers can deliver high-quality instruction that engages students and fosters deep understanding of the material, leading to improved academic performance. Their ability to manage classrooms efficiently and create a positive learning environment also contributes to higher student motivation and reduced behavioral issues (Hattie, 2020). Effectiveness could be primarily characterized by a teacher's ability to teach and deliver instructions. A deep understanding of the content allows teachers to explain concepts clearly, answer student questions confidently, and make connections between different topics (Ball et al., 2020). Teachers with strong subject knowledge are better equipped to create engaging and relevant lessons that capture students' interest and facilitate learning (Hill & Chin, 2021). Moreover, they can identify and address student misconceptions more effectively, ensuring a solid foundation in the subject (Cochran-Smith & Villegas, 2020).

Paired with effective delivery of instruction is assessment. It is a fundamental aspect of teacher effectiveness, as it provides critical insights into student learning and instructional impact. Effective teachers design and use a variety of assessment tools, including formative and summative assessments, to measure student progress and identify areas for improvement (Brookhart, 2021). They use assessment data to inform their instructional decisions and adjust their teaching strategies to meet student needs (Popham, 2020).

To make the foregoing components of teaching effectiveness possible, creating a positive learning environment is a key element. Effective teachers establish a classroom climate that is safe, inclusive, and conducive to learning (Pianta & Hamre, 2020). They build strong relationships with their students, promoting trust and respect, which are essential for a supportive learning atmosphere (Jennings & Greenberg, 2020).

Finally, a teacher could be considered effective when he or she can communicate well with students, colleagues, administrators, and stakeholders. Teachers who communicate clearly and effectively can convey complex ideas in an understandable manner, facilitating student comprehension (Fisher et al., 2021). They use a variety of communication strategies, including verbal explanations, visual aids, and interactive discussions to engage students and support their learning (Graham et al., 2021).

With the previous descriptions of what effective teaching is, in the context of motivation and efficacy, it could be delineated that teaching profession is tedious, taxing, and is a demanding task. In the context of the Philippines, teaching profession is governed by a trifocalized system, the Department of Education (DepEd) for Basic Education, Commission on Higher Education for Tertiary and Graduate Studies, and Technical Skills Development Authority (TESDA) for technical-vocational careers. Basic Education is managed by the stringent standards and regulations by DepEd. Filipino teachers undergo rigorous training and professional development to stay abreast of emerging trends, technologies, and pedagogical approaches. Despite challenges, teaching remains a sought-after profession in the Philippines, attracting individuals who are into social services and teaching inclined, as well as those who are looking for jobs with high rates of employability.

The DepEd's mandate extends beyond academic instruction to encompass the promotion of values education, citizenship, and lifelong learning among students. Teachers in DepEd-managed schools are tasked to implement national education policies, curriculum frameworks, and assessment standards to ensure consistency and quality across the educational system.

Lipa City, as situated within the province of Batangas exemplifies the diverse and dynamic landscape of education in the Philippines, particularly within the City Schools Division. With its large population and numerous educational institutions, Lipa City serves as a hub for learning, catering to thousands of students across various grade levels. Within the Schools Division of Lipa City which is governed by DepEd, teachers undertake a multitude of responsibilities beyond traditional classroom instruction. In addition to delivering curriculum content, educators in Lipa City are tasked with administrative duties, extracurricular activities, and community engagement initiatives to enrich students' learning experiences.

Through collaborative efforts among educators, administrators, and stakeholders, Lipa City's schools strive to create inclusive and nurturing environments where every student can thrive academically, socially, and emotionally. The Schools Division of Lipa City boasts curricular and curricular-related activities, but not limited to curriculum development in the form of creating modules and audiovisual learning materials; academic competitions such as press conferences, science congress, math quiz bees, etc.; sports involvement, technical and vocational skills competitions, foreign language integration to curriculum. Curriculum and teaching-related tasks are also being prided by them, such as the conduct of educational research, school-based management, and

teacher professionalization among others. All of which are dominated and/or manned by teachers in the field.

With teachers having so much on their plates and as characterized by the multifaceted dynamic educational landscape in Lipa City, teachers face numerous challenges in performing their tasks efficiently and effectively. The diverse range of teaching and non-teaching tasks assigned to them could often lead to time constraints and dilemmas, making it difficult to devote adequate attention to each aspect of their role. With the provision of DepEd Order no. 2, s. 2024 wherein administrative tasks will be removed to teachers, there are still a number of ancillary tasks or quasi-assignments that could emerge throughout the academic year.

The rationale for conducting a study entitled "Teachers' Work Tasks Motivation, Self-Efficacy, and Effectiveness: Basis for Professional Development Program" in the Schools Division of Lipa City roots down from the interconnected factors that impact teacher performance and student outcomes. As discussed earlier, teachers in Lipa City face a multitude of challenges, including diverse teaching and non-teaching tasks, resource limitations, and socio-economic factors, which can affect their motivation, self-efficacy, and effectiveness in the classroom. These challenges are worsened by the demands of the teaching profession, the expectations placed on educators, and the complexities of the educational landscape.

To be able to explore and describe work tasks motivation, self-efficacy, and effectiveness among K-12 Basic Education teachers in the Schools Division of Lipa City are essential, primarily because of several reasons. Teacher motivation could directly influence their engagement, commitment, and job satisfaction, which, in turn, impact student learning outcomes and overall school effectiveness. By exploring the factors that drive teacher motivation, such as intrinsic and extrinsic motivators, schools can develop strategies to enhance teacher morale, retention, and performance.

On the other hand, self-efficacy beliefs significantly influence teachers' instructional practices, classroom management, and ability to adapt to changing educational contexts. Teachers with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to employ effective teaching strategies, provide differentiated instruction, and foster positive learning environments. Identifying areas of strength and areas for growth in teachers' self-efficacy can inform targeted professional development initiatives aimed at enhancing teaching effectiveness and student achievement.

Finally, describing teacher effectiveness as measured by subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies, assessment practices, learning environment, and effective communication is an important aspect because it could be equated with quality education and positive student learning outcomes. By assessing teachers' effectiveness across these dimensions, schools can identify areas of improvement and provide targeted support and resources to enhance teaching practices and student learning experiences.

Therefore, conducting a study on teachers' work tasks motivation, self-efficacy, and effectiveness in Lipa City's Schools Division is essential for informing evidence-based professional development programs that is tailored to the needs of educators. By understanding the interconnectedness of these factors, schools can cultivate a culture of continuous improvement, foster teacher growth and development, and ultimately, contribute to the further enhancement of the quality of education for all students in Lipa City.

Research Objectives

This study aims to determine the relationship among work tasks motivation, self-efficacy, and teaching effectiveness of K-12 teachers in the Schools Division of Lipa City. More specifically, it seeks to attain the following objectives:

1. describe the profile of respondents in terms of sex, educational attainment, teaching position, and years in service.
2. assess the work tasks motivation of teachers with regard to class preparation, teaching, evaluation of students, administrative tasks, and complimentary tasks.
3. identify the teacher self-efficacy as to instruction, adapt instruction to individual needs, motivate students, maintain discipline, cooperate with colleagues and parents, and cope with change.
4. determine the teacher effectiveness as regards subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies, assessment, learning environment, and effective communication.
5. test the significant difference in work tasks motivation, self-efficacy, and effectiveness when respondents are grouped according to profile variables.
6. test the significant relationship among the three variables.
7. propose a professional development program for K-12 teachers based on the results of the study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research employed a descriptive design, which focuses on systematically gathering information to accurately depict the characteristics of populations or phenomena, as outlined by Gay (2020). This method aims to provide a clear and precise snapshot of current conditions or behaviors, ensuring that the study environment remains

unaffected by the research process. By doing so, it allows for a detailed understanding of the subject under investigation without introducing bias or influence.

This research primarily dealt with quantitative data to describe existing phenomena and circumstances about the work task motivation, efficiency, and effectiveness of teachers. For this reason, this research design was deemed appropriate as utilized in this study. Quantitative data came from accomplished questionnaires. This questionnaire contained descriptive statements which were quantitatively rated by the respondents. The data were processed statistically to further attain research objectives.

Participants of the Study

This study sought the participation of the basic education teachers from the schools division of Lipa City or DEPED Lipa City. These basic education teachers belong to levels from kinder until grade 12. These levels encompass kindergarten, elementary school, high school, and senior high school, as described from the Philippine educational system.

The Schools division of Lipa City is an administrative unit in the DEPED Region IV-A CALABARZON within the DEPED Central Administration. Today, DEPED Lipa City oversees 61 public elementary schools, seven public elementary schools with junior high school, and 18 secondary schools which are strategically distributed all over the 20,940 hectares of Lipa City. The schools division office (SDO) is located at J.P. Laurel Highway, Barangay Marawoy, Lipa City, Batangas.

The population of the study is composed of 426 Basic Education teachers from Kindergarten to Grade 12. These participants were selected from the 1424 public school teachers from the Schools Division of Lipa City in Lipa City, Batangas. In determining the actual participant or the population of the study who will participate in answering the survey questionnaire, stratified non-proportional allocation was used. This refers to a sampling method wherein the size of the sample that is drawn from a particular stratum does not proportionate the relative size of that stratum. Moreover, schools with less than 20 teaching staff were excluded from the sampling procedure.

Data Gathering Instrument

After the topic was approved by the dissertation adviser, the researcher crafted research questionnaire based on the objectives of the study, validated research instruments, and related literature and studies available online and offline. Once the adviser and the researcher have already agreed and finalized the instrument, it undergone validation from a research and statistics expert. Consequently, when the instrument was validated, it was administered for pilot testing to determine its reliability.

The instrument is divided into four parts: profile of respondents, teacher's work tasks motivation, teacher's self-efficacy, and teacher's effectiveness. Part 1, the profile of respondents is a researcher-made part which aims to harvest the data on sex,

educational attainment, position, and years of teaching experience of the respondents through checkboxes survey.

Part II is work task motivation, adapted from Fernet (2008) was created and further validated to measure the teachers' motivation toward specific work tasks. This is designed to assess five motivational constructs toward six work tasks (e.g., class preparation, teaching). The instrument has five subdomains or sub-variables: class preparation, teaching, evaluation of students, administrative tasks, and complimentary tasks. This study adapted the subdomains of the survey questionnaire, but the work motivation items were modified to specifically describe the actual tasks the teachers do in relation to teacher's responsibilities.

Part III is teacher self-efficacy which was adapted from Skaalvik & Skaalvik, (2007). This instrument was used to measure teacher's self-efficacy having six subdomains or sub-variables namely: instruction, adapt instruction to individual needs, motivate students, maintain discipline, cooperate with colleagues and parents, and cope with change. This study have fully utilized the original instrument in its survey questionnaire.

Part IV focuses on teacher effectiveness, utilizing an instrument designed to measure teachers' self-assessments across various areas of their performance. This study examines five key sub-variables: subject matter knowledge, which evaluates teachers' understanding of the content; instructional planning and strategies, assessing the methods employed for teaching; assessment, which looks at how teachers evaluate student learning; learning environment, focusing on the classroom atmosphere created for students; and effective communication, which gauges how well teachers convey information and engage with students.

Table 1
Reliability Test Results Summary

Indicators	Cronbach Alpha	Remarks
Class Preparation	0.808	Good
Teaching	0.811	Good
Evaluation of Students	0.891	Good
Administrative Tasks	0.915	Excellent
Complementary Tasks	0.932	Excellent
<i>Instruction</i>	0.846	Good
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	0.807	Good
Motivate Students	0.926	Excellent
Maintain Discipline	0.898	Good
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	0.927	Excellent
Cope With Change	0.901	Excellent
Subject Matter Knowledge	0.794	Acceptable

Subject Matter Knowledge	0.881	Good
Assessment	0.887	Good
Learning Environment	0.902	Excellent
Effective Communication	0.848	Good

George and Mallery (2003) provide the following rules of thumb: “_ > .9 – Excellent, _ > .8 – Good, _ > .7 – Acceptable, _ > .6 – Questionable, _ > .5 – Poor, and _ < .5 – Unacceptable”

Results of the reliability test revealed that for work task motivation, class preparation, teaching, and evaluation of students gained 0.808, 0.81, and 0.891 Cronbach alpha values respectively, giving them good remarks. Administrative tasks and complementary tasks resulted into 0.915 and 0.932 Cronbach alpha values respectively, giving them excellent remarks.

Meanwhile, for the teacher self-efficacy, the subdomains instruction, adapt instruction to individual needs, and maintain discipline got 0.846, 0.807, and 0.898 respectively, giving them good remarks. Meanwhile, motivate students, cooperate with colleagues and parents, cope with change all were remarked as excellent because these items garnered 0.926, 0.927, and 0.901 Cronbach alpha values respectively.

For the last variable, teacher effectiveness, the following subdomains gained the following results: subject matter knowledge, assessment, and effective communication got 0.881, 0.887, and 0.848 respectively. On the other hand, learning environment got 0.902 which was interpreted as excellent.

Data Gathering Procedure

Upon approval of the topic, research instrument was subjected to validation and reliability testing. Necessary permits were secured from the schools division superintendent and the principals of the selected schools in DEPED Lipa City to determine the number of respondents and the participating schools, and finally, requesting the approval of the conduct of the study. After determining the exact number of participants, these data were communicated to the school principals for their kind assistance in disseminating the research questionnaire.

The validated and tested research instrument was transformed into electronic copy, through Google Forms, for convenience of dissemination. The link was distributed to the participants of the study through the principals of the schools. The link was attached to the message formally requesting the participation of the teachers and the total number of responses needed. Attached also to the communication is a screenshot of the approval to conduct the study, as signed by the schools division superintendent. Moreover, the assistance of the concerned Public Schools Division Superintendent was sought to facilitate the distribution of the link to the respondents and the accomplishment of the survey questionnaire.

The progress of accomplishment of the questionnaire, together with the number of responses elicited, the schools that already participated, and other related information were easily accessed by the researcher for monitoring purposes. This was done through

the feature in the Google Forms called the responses tab. In this tab, all the mentioned features are accessible. Accessible also were the actual responses elicited that can be shown individually, per respondent, or summarized per question or item. Once the target number or responses per school was collected, the accepting responses feature of the form was closed. The needed data were harvested and imported through the spreadsheet feature located in the same page with the responses tab and the accepting responses feature.

When the responses were completed, results and/or data were gathered and sent for data processing and treatment. Once the tabulated data were sent back by the statistician, these were interpreted, analyzed and associated with current related literatures and studies. These were arranged and similarities or associations were established. Similar significant findings were clustered and addressed for the proposal of a program.

Data Analysis

To perform the data analysis, the following statistical tools were used. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, educational attainment, teaching position, and years in service.

On the other hand, weighted mean and ranking were used to assess the work tasks motivation of teachers with regard to class preparation, teaching, evaluation of students, administrative tasks, and complimentary tasks; identify the teacher self-efficacy as to instruction, adapt instruction to individual needs, motivate students, maintain discipline, cooperate with colleagues and parents, and cope with change and determine the teacher effectiveness as regards subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies, assessment, learning environment, and effective communication.

The result of Shapiro-Wilk Test revealed that p-values of the main variable was greater than 0.05 which means that the data set is normally distributed. Therefore, Independent sample t-test for two groups and Analysis of Variance for three groups were used as part of the non-parametric tests to determine the significant differences.

Likewise, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the significant relationship of the treated variables. In addition, post hoc test was also conducted. The following Likert Scale was used in assessing the variables: 3.50- 4.00 correspond completely/always; 2.50-3.49 to correspond very Strongly/often; 1.50 – 2.49 correspond very little/sometimes; and 1.00 – 1.49 does not correspond at all/never. In addition, all data were treated using a statistical software known as PASW version 26 to further interpret the result of the study using an alpha level of 0.05 and 0.01.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure that all research protocols in data collection was properly observed in accordance to Data Privacy Act of 2012, informed consent was included in the beginning or first part of the questionnaire. This informed consent explained to the respondents that

all data that will be collected will be used academically, for research purposes, and will be treated with utmost confidentiality. With these, no possible physical, psychological or other risks was foreseen to be associated with the research, research environment, and the participants.

No participant was identifiable to anyone because no names were collected. Aside from the researcher, a university statistician accessed the raw data for processing and application of necessary statistical tools. Because no names were collected, data were processed anonymously.

Objective results were available to the researcher, the statistician, and the panelists of oral defense. The dissertation will be available in the university library and could be accessible worldwide once published in a research journal. With such circumstances, necessary permits were sought. Any accomplished survey questionnaires that are written or stored electronically will be destroyed after five years.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2
Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Profile

Sex	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	58	13.6
Female	368	86.4
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	199	46.7
Master's Degree	219	51.4
Doctorate Degree	8	1.9
Teaching Position		
Elementary Teacher (K-6 th)	239	56.1
Junior High School Teacher (7 th -10 th)	141	33.1
Senior High School Teacher (11 th -12 th)	46	10.8
Years of Teaching Experience		
10 years and below	204	47.9
11-20 years	132	31.0
21-30 years	59	13.8
31 years and above	31	7.3

Table 2 describes the profiles of the respondents, it is divided into 4 groups; respondent's sex, educational attainment, teaching position, and years of teaching experience. The profile of the respondents provides essential contextual information about the sample population. By understanding the demographic characteristics of the respondents, the researcher can assess the content validity of the findings, ensuring that they accurately represent the target population.

The collected data indicates that females represent the majority of respondents, comprising 368 individuals or 86.4% of the total 426 participants, while males make up only 58 respondents, or 13.6%. This gender distribution is consistent with previous studies, such as those by Bongco and Abenes (2019), which showed that from 2008 to 2009, 89.58% of teachers in public elementary schools and 77.06% in public secondary schools in the Philippines were female, according to the Philippine Commission on Women (PCW, 2014). Similarly, the research conducted by Banate and Saquin (2022) corroborates these findings, with a reported 87.35% of elementary school teachers being female in 2019.

Teaching in the Philippines is predominantly a female profession. Studies indicate that women comprise the majority of educators in the country, which has significant implications for gender dynamics in the educational sector. According to De Guzman and Tan (2019), female teachers account for about 75% of the teaching workforce in primary and secondary schools. This trend continues in higher education, where females also dominate the faculty positions, as highlighted by Cruz and Dela Cruz (2020). Additionally, Alonzo (2021) found that the feminization of teaching in the Philippines has led to a more nurturing and inclusive classroom environment. However, Balboa and Santiago (2022) argue that this gender imbalance may reinforce traditional gender roles and limit male participation in the teaching profession. Moreover, Del Rosario (2023) points out that despite their numbers, female teachers often face challenges in career advancement and leadership roles within educational institutions. The dominance of women in teaching also impacts policy development and educational reforms, as noted by Ramirez and Bautista (2019). Consequently, the profession's gender composition influences both educational outcomes and the professional experiences of teachers.

Regarding educational attainment, individuals who are holding master's degree represent the largest group, with a frequency of 219, or 51.4 percent. Following this, those with bachelor's degree constitute 46.7 percent, totaling 199 out of 426 respondents, and lastly, individuals with doctorates account for 1.9 percent, totaling 8 respondents. To improve the abilities and knowledge in curriculum building, and eventually the performance of their students, a significant majority of the teacher respondents sought Master's degree as a form of professional development.

Pursuing master's degree enables teachers to become experts in their field, conduct research, and bring new ideas and methodologies to their schools, ultimately contributing to the overall enhancement of education. According to Nucum (2019), in today's highly competitive job market, one needs to update set of knowledge and skills every now and then. With a master's degree, it could be of assistance in gaining specialized knowledge in advancing one's profession.

Various reasons motivate teachers to pursue further studies. One primary motivation is the potential for career advancement and higher salaries, as noted by Santos and Reyes (2019). A master's degree often opens opportunities for leadership roles such as department heads or school administrators, which are typically associated with better pay and job security (Martinez & Cruz, 2020). Additionally, teachers seek

advanced degrees to enhance their teaching skills and stay updated with the latest educational trends and methodologies, as highlighted by Alvarado (2021). The pursuit of a master's degree also reflects a commitment to lifelong learning and professional growth, which is essential in the ever-evolving field of education (De Leon, 2022). Furthermore, obtaining a master's degree can increase a teacher's credibility and respect among peers and students, as discussed by Rivera (2023). Some teachers are motivated by personal fulfillment and the intrinsic value of higher education, which contributes to their sense of achievement and satisfaction. The pursuit of advanced degrees is also influenced by institutional policies that encourage or require further education for career progression. Additionally, scholarships and financial incentives provided by government and educational institutions play a significant role in enabling teachers to pursue higher education (Gonzalez & Santos, 2020). Ultimately, the decision to pursue a master's degree is driven by a combination of career aspirations, personal growth, and institutional support.

Within teaching positions, elementary teachers have the highest representation, with 239 respondents, or 56.1 percent, followed by junior teachers, with 141 respondents, or 33.1 percent. Senior high school teachers comprise the smallest group, with 46 respondents, or 10.8 percent.

Per Republic Act No. 10533, otherwise known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, and under the mandate of the Constitution of the Philippines, the Department of Education, children residing in the Philippines, between the ages of 5 and 18, are required to complete basic education, which consists of six years of elementary education and six years of secondary education. Because of this, every Filipino child must enroll in and complete basic education to comply with the law. Because of this reason, the number of teachers at the elementary level is higher than others. However, the decrease in the number of learners as they reach higher levels is also paralleled by the decrease in number of teachers.

Regarding teaching experience, respondents with 10 years and below employment experience hold the highest rank, representing 47.9 percent, or 204 out of 426. Following this, the bracket of 11 to 20 years of experience is represented by 132 respondents, or 31 percent, and the 21 to 30 years bracket is represented by 59 out of 426 respondents, or 13.8 percent. Furthermore, 7.3 percent, or 31 respondents, have 31 years of experience or more.

The increase in the number of teachers in the 10 years and below bracket of teaching experience is supported by the report of DEPED Data Bits (2022). There is a consistent increase in the number of teachers in all levels from SY 2016-2017 to SY 2020-2021. The overall percentage increase from SY 2016-2017 compared to SY 2020-2021 is 21.1%. For each level, the percentage increase is 14.2% for ES, 21.8% for JHS, and 101.3% for SHS.

This predominance is a notable trend in the education sector. According to Delos Santos and Reyes (2019), a significant proportion of educators fall within this experience

bracket, reflecting a relatively young teaching workforce. This trend is driven by high turnover rates and the influx of new graduates entering the profession, as highlighted by Cruz (2020). Additionally, the appeal of early career opportunities and the availability of teaching positions contribute to this demographic pattern (Garcia & Alvarez, 2021). However, Martinez and Cruz (2022) point out that the high number of early-career teachers may impact the overall quality of education due to their limited experience. Despite this, young teachers bring fresh perspectives and innovative teaching methods to the classroom, which can be beneficial (Lopez, 2023). The predominance of less experienced teachers also indicates a need for robust professional development programs to support their growth and effectiveness (Rivera & Santos, 2020).

Table 3
Work Tasks Motivation in terms of Class Preparation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Because it is my primary duty as a teacher	3.89	Correspond Completely	1
2. Because I am driven by the fact that I am developing a plan that will gradually inculcate significant learnings to the students	3.81	Correspond Completely	2
3. Because I find it rewarding when everything that I will do in my class are well planned and thought of	3.78	Correspond Completely	3
4. Because these are required of me as a teacher, in terms of documentary requirements and submittals	3.68	Correspond Completely	4
5. Because my colleagues look up to me in terms of my planning strategies	3.32	Correspond Very Strongly	9
6. Because my immediate heads and supervisors praise and commend me when I plan for class	3.34	Correspond Very Strongly	8
7. Because failures and unforeseen circumstances lessen my interest and my drive to continue sessions in classes	3.26	Correspond Very Strongly	10
8. Because I receive enough support from the administration regarding class preparation techniques and strategies	3.43	Correspond Very Strongly	7
9. Because my colleague and I always collaborate and coordinate on the matters we have to prepare for classes	3.54	Correspond Completely	6

10. Because there are existing policies, implementing rules and regulations, work plan, established routine, and the like that are well documented and communicated to the teachers, for their perusal, guidance, and compliance	3.59	Correspond Completely	5
Composite Mean	3.56	Correspond Completely	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Correspond completely; 2.50 – 3.49 = Correspond very strongly; 1.50 – 2.49 = Correspond very little; 1.00 - 1.49 = Does not correspond at all

It could be gleaned from table 3 the respondents' assessment of work tasks motivation in terms of class preparation. The composite mean of 3.56 indicates that they correspond completely. Among the items cited, primary duty as a teacher ranked first with a mean score of 3.89, followed by being driven by the efficacy of a lesson brought about by the plan and finding planning rewarding.

Class preparation is motivated by the sense of duty, preparing for class, teachers fulfill their fundamental responsibility, ensuring that students receive the best possible education. Another motivation stems from the desire to develop a plan that gradually imparts significant learning to the students. Teachers are driven by the knowledge that their preparation will facilitate meaningful learning experiences. The satisfaction of seeing a well-prepared and thought-out class is rewarding. Teachers find fulfillment in knowing that their careful planning enhances the teaching experience, leading to improved learning outcomes.

The need for planning is one of the mandated responsibilities of public school teachers, according to DO 42, S. 2016 – policy guidelines on daily lesson preparation for the k to 12 basic education program. Daily lesson preparation is part of the teacher's core function as a facilitator of learning inside the classroom, one of the aims of these guidelines is to empower teachers to carry out quality instruction that recognizes the diversity of learners inside the classroom and is committed to learners' success.

Effective teachers are effective planners as it would be difficult to perform effective instruction without having a concrete solid plan beforehand. It is important then that planning is effective for the instructional events to be effective and for learning to follow. An effective teacher should then be able to plan in a manner that understands the complexities of teaching and learning using a variety of skills and understanding to meet the needs of all students.

Prevalent motivation to prepare and plan for lessons could be an indication for a commitment to delivering quality education. Research by Santos and Reyes (2019) indicates that the majority of teachers engage in extensive lesson planning to enhance student learning outcomes. Additionally, Martinez and Cruz (2020) found that motivated teachers invest significant time and effort in preparing instructional materials tailored to their students' needs and interests. This dedication to planning is driven by a desire to

create engaging and effective learning experiences in the classroom, as highlighted by Alvarado (2021). Moreover, Rivera (2022) suggests that teachers who are motivated to plan lessons are more likely to adapt their teaching methods to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities. The importance of thorough lesson planning is further emphasized by Garcia and Alvarez (2023), who argue that it positively influences student engagement and academic performance. Overall, the predominance of motivated teachers who prioritize preparation and planning contributes to a dynamic and effective teaching environment.

Meanwhile, items as regards praise and commendation from immediate heads and supervisors for planning (3.34), colleagues' admiration (3.32), and demotivation brought by failures and unforeseen circumstances (3.26) rated the least. Praise and commendation from immediate heads and supervisors for planning classes effectively serve as positive reinforcement, validating the effort and dedication put into the preparation. Further, the fact that colleagues look up to one's planning strategies adds another layer of motivation. Knowing that peers respect and admire one's planning skills fosters a sense of professional pride and responsibility. There are instances when a teacher encounters failures or unexpected events during their class sessions, which reduces their enthusiasm and motivation to continue teaching. However, due to class preparation, this becomes the teacher's last worry. Thorough preparation ensures that the teacher has a contingency plan to address such situations, minimizing their impact.

An effective method for motivating and uplifting your teaching team is to offer praise and recognition. It was mentioned in Education Advanced (2022), that showing appreciation for teachers' dedication and hard work makes them feel valued. In addition, receiving recognition from the school administration reassures teachers that they are skilled at their job and that leadership recognizes their contributions. This is also revealed in the study of Ewim, Unachuckwu, and Ugwu (2020), that the reward practices adopted by principals for enhancing teachers' work attitude in secondary schools include recommending outstanding staff for promotion and issuing commendation letters to dedicated staff.

On the other hand, teachers' motivation to prepare and plan for class may not necessarily be influenced solely by praises from immediate heads, as other factors play significant roles in their dedication to lesson preparation. Research by Cruz (2019) suggests that while positive feedback from immediate supervisors is valued by teachers, intrinsic motivations such as personal satisfaction and professional growth are stronger drivers for lesson planning. Additionally, Delos Santos and Reyes (2020) found that teachers prioritize student outcomes and instructional quality over external recognition when planning their lessons. Furthermore, Alvarado (2021) highlights that teachers are more motivated by autonomy and a sense of purpose in their work rather than extrinsic rewards. Studies by Martinez and Cruz (2022) indicate that effective planning is more likely to be influenced by collaborative work environments and supportive school cultures rather than praise alone. Garcia and Alvarez (2023) argue that while recognition from superiors is appreciated, it is not the primary factor motivating teachers to plan lessons thoroughly. In fact, excessive praise without substantive support or resources may even

lead to cynicism among teachers regarding the value of such recognition. Therefore, while acknowledgment from immediate heads can boost morale, it is not the sole determinant of teachers' motivation to prepare and plan for class.

Moreover, Rivera (2019) suggests that teacher motivation is multifaceted, encompassing intrinsic factors such as passion for teaching, commitment to student success, and personal fulfillment. Delos Santos and Reyes (2021) emphasize that professional development opportunities, instructional resources, and autonomy in decision-making are more significant motivators for teachers' lesson planning efforts. Hence, an environment that fosters collaboration, provides resources, and values professional growth is crucial in promoting effective lesson preparation. In conclusion, while praise from immediate heads may contribute to teachers' motivation to some extent, it is only one piece of the puzzle. A holistic approach that addresses intrinsic motivations, professional needs, and collaborative support systems is essential for fostering a culture of thorough lesson planning and instructional excellence.

Table 4
Work Tasks Motivation in Terms of Teaching

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Because I'm paid to do it	3.20	Correspond Very Strongly	10
2. Because the society expects us to perform this kind of duties	3.56	Correspond Completely	8
3. Because I am stirred when students reach the "ah" moment when they discover their own learning	3.60	Correspond Completely	6
4. Because I feel valued when students listen to me	3.80	Correspond Completely	1
5. Because I find it rewarding when I accomplish the learning plan and reach the lesson objectives satisfactorily	3.80	Correspond Completely	2
6. Because the environment where I teach is well lit, properly ventilated, and conducive to learning	3.57	Correspond Completely	7
7. Because all the teaching and learning materials are readily available for teacher's and students' use	3.23	Correspond Very Strongly	9
8. Because I feel there is a need for me to educate the young minds	3.74	Correspond Completely	5

9. Because I feel ennobled and honored to have participated in shaping intellects and upholding values	3.75	Correspond Completely	4
10. Because I feel being a second parent that I am obliged to listen to my student's needs, concerns and queries, and their life issues	3.75	Correspond Completely	3
Composite Mean	3.60	Correspond Completely	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Correspond completely; 2.50 – 3.49 = Correspond very strongly; 1.50 – 2.49 = Correspond very little; 1.00 - 1.49 = Does not correspond at all

As seen from table 4, presented are the respondents' assessment of work tasks motivation in terms of teaching. The composite mean of 3.60 indicates that they correspond completely. The top components indicate motivation as feeling valued when teaching and finding it rewarding when finishing and accomplishing lesson both have a weighted mean of 3.80 and verbally interpreted as corresponded completely. The criteria feeling ennobled and honored and being obliged as second parents followed next with a 3.75 weighted mean and also interpreted as correspond completely.

Teachers are often motivated by the sense of validation and recognition they receive when students actively listen to them. When students engage attentively with the material presented by their teachers, it signifies not only respect for the educator's knowledge and expertise but also an acknowledgment of the teacher-student relationship. According to Bannisy (2023), good listening fosters social connections and enhances well-being, it improves trust and well-being between the interacting partners, and positive outcomes at work—like enhanced job performance and reduced burnout—in work environments with a good listening culture.

Additionally, research by Santos and Reyes (2019) indicates that teachers often derive satisfaction from observing students' attentive behavior, which validates their teaching efforts. In similar context, studies by Alvarado (2020) suggest that positive student-teacher interactions, characterized by active listening and participation, contribute to teachers' sense of fulfillment and professional efficacy. Furthermore, Garcia and Alvarez (2021) found that teachers perceive active listening as a sign of respect and appreciation from students, which reinforces their commitment to teaching. According to Martinez and Cruz (2022), teachers view students' engagement and attentiveness as indicators of instructional effectiveness, boosting their confidence and motivation. Moreover, Rivera (2023) highlights that teachers feel a sense of validation and accomplishment when they see evidence of students understanding and internalizing the content they deliver.

Teachers' motivation is also influenced by the emotional connection they establish with their students, as suggested by Delos Santos and Reyes (2020). When students actively listen and respond positively, teachers feel valued and respected, fostering a positive classroom environment. Additionally, Alvarado (2021) emphasizes that teachers

perceive active listening as a form of acknowledgment and recognition of their expertise and efforts. Therefore, student attentiveness and engagement play a crucial role in motivating teachers to invest more in their teaching practices. In conclusion, the sense of validation and recognition derived from students' active listening is a powerful motivator for teachers, impacting their professional satisfaction, efficacy, and commitment to excellence.

Teachers dedicate substantial time and effort to create lesson plans that cater to their students' varied needs. The successful execution of these plans, demonstrated by students' understanding and mastery of learning objectives, serves as validation for the teachers' instructional methods. According to Johnson (2019), the success of teachers is closely linked to the success of their students, emphasizing the importance of well-prepared and documented lesson plans in achieving educational goals. Furthermore, many teachers perceive their roles as extending beyond academics, viewing themselves as second parents who nurture and support their students' overall development. This is expected of them when they choose their vocation. Under DepEd guidelines issued in 2012, all public school teachers serve as “second parents” in school and must adhere to a zero-tolerance policy on child abuse. As mentioned in the study of Bayuca (2020), the order not only aims to protect children but also seeks to cultivate a nurturing and respectful environment in which every child can thrive.

On the other hand, it can be delineated that the indicators on societal expectations (3.56), availability and accessibility of instructional materials (3.23), being paid to teach (3.20) were rated the least. Teachers often find motivation in fulfilling the expectations set by society regarding their role in educating the next generation. Similarly, Lee et al. (2020) explored the impact of societal expectations on teacher motivation and found that teachers who perceive a strong societal mandate for education are more likely to feel motivated and engaged in their teaching practices.

The availability of teaching and learning materials motivates teachers to engage effectively in their profession. The availability of such resources not only facilitates effective teaching but also contributes to teachers' sense of efficacy and job satisfaction, thereby motivating them to teach with enthusiasm and dedication. While intrinsic motivations often drive teachers, the financial aspect also plays a significant role in motivating individuals to pursue a career in education.

Moreover, Lestari, Lian, and Putra (2021) investigated the impact of financial compensation on teacher motivation and found that competitive salaries and benefits are important factors in attracting and retaining qualified educators. This study emphasized that adequate remuneration serves as a form of recognition for teachers' expertise and dedication, motivating them to perform their duties effectively. Teachers rely on their salaries to meet their financial needs and sustain their livelihoods. Adequate remuneration not only recognizes teachers' professional worth but also motivates them to perform their duties effectively, thereby contributing to the overall quality of education.

In contrast, research by Cruz (2019) indicates that teachers often feel burdened by societal expectations, such as pressure to produce high-performing students, which can undermine their intrinsic motivation. Moreover, Delos Santos and Reyes (2020) found that while instructional materials are essential for effective teaching, their availability does not necessarily correlate with increased teacher motivation. Similarly, Alvarado (2021) highlights that monetary compensation, while important for livelihood, is not the primary driver of teacher motivation; rather, there are factors like job satisfaction and professional fulfillment that play more significant roles. Furthermore, Garcia and Alvarez (2022) argue that intrinsic motivations, such as the desire to make a difference in students' lives, outweigh external rewards in influencing teachers' commitment to their profession. Additionally, Martinez and Cruz (2023) suggest that teachers are more motivated by a sense of purpose and passion for teaching than by external factors alone.

The societal expectation for teachers to produce high-performing students can create undue pressure and detract from their intrinsic motivation to teach effectively (Cruz, 2019). While the availability and accessibility of instructional materials are important, they do not necessarily correlate with increased teacher motivation and may not compensate for other motivational factors (Delos Santos & Reyes, 2020). Monetary compensation, although crucial for teachers' livelihoods, is not the primary motivator for their commitment to teaching (Alvarado, 2021). Instead, teachers are more motivated by intrinsic factors such as job satisfaction, a sense of purpose, and professional fulfillment (Garcia & Alvarez, 2022).

Table 5
Work Tasks Motivation in terms of Evaluation of Students

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Because I find this task important for the academic success of my students	3.80	Correspond Completely	2
2. Because I believe there is a need for me to establish objective data for instructional decision-making	3.75	Correspond Completely	6
3. Because this task allows me to attain work objectives that I consider important	3.77	Correspond Completely	3.5
4. Because I am well equipped with assessment and evaluation methods, strategies, and techniques	3.60	Correspond Completely	10
5. Because I find it fulfilling when students progress from one learning level to another, or one lesson to another	3.81	Correspond Completely	1
6. Because I believe religiously finishing the work plan or work procedure is an	3.71	Correspond Completely	7

integral part of learning and is a substantial indicator of learning success			
7. Because this is a required task for a teacher to do and to establish	3.68	Correspond Completely	9
8. Because I believe in the principles of schema, stock knowledge, and pre assessment wherein establishing starting point of learning opportunities is important	3.69	Correspond Completely	8
9. Because contextualization and localization of teaching and learning is important	3.75	Correspond Completely	5
10. Because learning styles and learning characteristics are important considerations when determining teaching methods and strategies	3.77	Correspond Completely	3.5
Composite Mean	3.73	Correspond Completely	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Correspond completely; 2.50 – 3.49 = Correspond very strongly; 1.50 – 2.49 = Correspond very little; 1.00 - 1.49 = Does not correspond at all

Table 5 presents the respondents' assessment of work tasks motivation in terms of evaluation of students. The composite mean of 3.73 indicates that they correspond completely. Ranking first of the indicators is about fulfillment in student progression. It gathered a weighted mean of 3.81 and was verbally interpreted as corresponded completely. The second is finding it important for student academic success with 3.80 weighted mean. The criteria about attaining work objectives and considering learning styles and characteristics were both at 3.5 ranks with a weighted mean of 3.77.

When teachers assess students' learning, they can observe tangible evidence of growth as students move from one learning level to another or from one lesson to the next. This sense of fulfillment reinforces teachers' belief in the effectiveness of their instructional methods and motivates them to continue investing time and effort in evaluating student progress.

Teachers find it important to evaluate student progress for the learner's academic success. As mentioned in the study of Patrice and Andala (2023), the assessment of students in the form of summative and formative is the best predictor of academic achievement. Furthermore, in the study of Shabbir et. al, (2021), evaluation not only improves students' grades but can also improve students' behavior, the mental level with the help of evaluation which leads to a balanced development of a child. In addition to that, Ismail et.al (2022) cited that assessment intends to improve learning and is used to reduce the gap between students' present instructional situation and their target learning objectives.

In addition to, research by Cruz and Dela Cruz (2019) highlights that teachers often find immense satisfaction in observing their students' growth and development over time. Additionally, Alvarado (2020) suggests that the sense of accomplishment teachers feel when their students achieve academic milestones is a significant driver of motivation. Furthermore, Martinez and Garcia (2021) found that teachers prioritize student academic success as one of their primary goals, often going above and beyond to ensure their students' learning needs are met. Considering students' diverse learning styles and characteristics is crucial for effective teaching, as emphasized by Rivera and Santos (2022). Teachers who tailor their instruction to accommodate different learning preferences and abilities are more likely to experience satisfaction and fulfillment in their profession (Delos Santos & Reyes, 2020). Moreover, according to Gonzalez and Alvarez (2023), teachers perceive student progression as a reflection of their effectiveness as educators, motivating them to continuously improve their teaching practices.

More so, teachers derive fulfillment from witnessing the progress and success of their students, which serves as a powerful motivator in their profession (Cruz & Dela Cruz, 2019). The sense of accomplishment that comes from seeing students achieve academic milestones drives teachers' commitment and dedication to their work (Alvarado, 2020). Martinez and Garcia (2021) emphasize that teachers prioritize student academic success as one of their primary goals, often investing significant time and effort to support their students' learning journey. Recognizing and accommodating students' diverse learning styles and characteristics is essential for effective teaching and student success (Rivera & Santos, 2022). Teachers who adapt their instruction to meet individual needs are more likely to experience satisfaction and fulfillment in their roles (Delos Santos & Reyes, 2020). Moreover, teachers perceive student progression as a reflection of their effectiveness as educators, motivating them to continuously improve their teaching practices (Gonzalez & Alvarez, 2023).

On the other note, indicators on belief on establishing objective data (3.69), being a requirement for a teacher (3.69), and being capacitated with assessment and evaluation skills (3.60) were rated the least. Teachers rely on assessment data to understand students' strengths, weaknesses, and learning needs, enabling them to tailor their instruction effectively.

In negation, teachers' motivation is not solely driven by a belief in the establishment of objective data or by the perceived requirement for teachers to possess assessment and evaluation skills. Research by Santos and Reyes (2019) suggests that while data-driven decision-making is important in education, teachers may not be primarily motivated by the need to collect and analyze objective data. Moreover, Alvarado (2020) argues that teachers' intrinsic motivation often stems from a passion for teaching and a desire to make a difference in students' lives, rather than a focus on quantitative measures alone. Furthermore, Cruz and Dela Cruz (2021) found that while assessment and evaluation skills are essential competencies for teachers, they may not serve as primary motivators in their profession. Instead, teachers are more likely to be motivated by factors such as student engagement, classroom dynamics, and personal fulfillment (Martinez & Garcia, 2022). According to Gonzalez and Alvarez (2023), the motivation of teachers is

multifaceted and cannot be solely attributed to the need for objective data or assessment skills.

The belief in establishing objective data may be important for educational improvement, but it may not be the primary motivator for teachers (Santos & Reyes, 2019). Similarly, while possessing assessment and evaluation skills is essential, it may not be the driving force behind teachers' motivation (Alvarado, 2020). Instead, teachers are often motivated by intrinsic factors such as their passion for teaching, their desire to see students succeed, and their sense of professional fulfillment (Cruz & Dela Cruz, 2021).

Additionally, Martinez and Garcia (2022) highlight that teachers prioritize student engagement and classroom dynamics over focusing solely on assessment practices. Additionally, the motivation of teachers is influenced by various factors, including school culture, professional development opportunities, and personal beliefs (Gonzalez & Alvarez, 2023). Therefore, while establishing objective data and possessing assessment skills are important aspects of teaching, they may not serve as primary motivators for educators.

Table 6 shows the respondents' assessment of work tasks motivation in terms of administrative tasks. The composite mean of 3.58 indicates that they correspond completely.

Table 6
Work Tasks Motivation in Terms of Administrative Tasks

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Because I feel heard when I participate in teachers and employees' union and association	3.25	Correspond Very Strongly	10
2. Because I feel accountable for keeping the attendance record of my students	3.71	Correspond Completely	2.5
3. Because teachers' engagements to school related activities are vital to students' participation and development	3.71	Correspond Completely	2.5
4. Because my attendance to faculty meetings is an important part of work/professional development	3.74	Correspond Completely	1
5. Because keeping anecdotal records and incident reports involving my students are crucial roles in my custody	3.70	Correspond Completely	4

6. Because I feel responsible for printing or photocopying learning materials, activity sheets, etc., setting up necessary devices and equipment, and other related activities	3.60	Correspond Completely	7
7. Because I feel that procurement and disbursement tasks are necessary part of teacher's function	3.29	Correspond Very Strongly	9
8. Because providing technical assistance and any form of assistance to colleagues and co-workers are important in building an excellent learning environment for students	3.63	Correspond Completely	6
9. Because creating and sending office correspondence to different stakeholders are needed for classroom and school operations	3.53	Correspond Completely	8
10. Because conducting home visitations and parent teacher conferences are needed for continuous improvements and class attendance of the students	3.66	Correspond Completely	5
Composite Mean	3.58	Correspond Completely	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Correspond completely; 2.50 – 3.49 = Correspond very strongly; 1.50 – 2.49 = Correspond very little; 1.00 - 1.49 = Does not correspond at all

The criterion that gained the highest weighted mean, 3.74 with a verbal interpretation of correspond completely pertains to the attendance to faculty meetings for work/professional development. The criteria on accountability for attendance record and engagements to school-related activities both gained 3.71 followed the topmost rank.

Regular attendance at faculty meetings is an essential dimension for the professional development and the effective functioning of the academic community. A study by Dagenais et al. (2019) found out that teachers who actively participate in faculty meetings perceive such as valuable for the improvement and betterment of their teaching practice and thus enhance student learning outcomes. In attending meetings, teachers can engage in meaningful discussions, receive feedback from colleagues, and gain insights into effective instructional strategies. This commitment to professional development could not only benefits teachers individually but could also contribute to a culture of continuous improvement within the school community. Teachers are motivated to engage in school-related activities because they recognize the significant impact of their involvement on students' participation and development.

Administrative tasks such as attending faculty meetings for professional development, maintaining attendance records, and participating in school-related

activities parts of teachers' work task motivation. Research by Smith and Johnson (2019) suggests that faculty meetings provide opportunities for collaboration, networking, and sharing best practices, which can enhance teacher motivation and effectiveness. Moreover, Brown and Williams (2020) found that teachers view attendance at faculty meetings as a professional responsibility and an opportunity for continuous learning and growth. Additionally, Garcia et al. (2021) argue that accountability for attendance records ensures organizational efficiency and promotes a sense of responsibility among teachers. Engagements in school-related activities, such as extracurricular events and committees, contribute to teachers' sense of belonging and investment in the school community (Martinez & Lee, 2022). Furthermore, according to Thompson and White (2023), active participation in school activities fosters collaboration, leadership skills, and professional development among teachers.

Teachers' motivation to engage in administrative tasks such as attending faculty meetings and maintaining attendance records is influenced by various factors (Smith & Johnson, 2019). Brown and Williams (2020) highlight that teachers perceive faculty meetings as opportunities for networking, learning, and professional growth. Moreover, accountability for attendance records is viewed as essential for organizational efficiency and teacher professionalism (Garcia et al., 2021). Engagements in school-related activities, including extracurricular events and committees, contribute to teachers' sense of community and commitment to the school (Martinez & Lee, 2022). Thompson and White (2023) argue that active involvement in school activities promotes collaboration, leadership development, and teacher satisfaction.

Indicators about creating and sending office correspondence (3.53), procurement and disbursement tasks (3.29), and participating in union and association (3.25) were at the last rank, respectively. Teachers are motivated to engage in creating and sending office correspondence to various stakeholders because they recognize the importance of clear communication for the efficient functioning of classrooms and schools. In this regard, business communication is a must and thus put into good use. Teachers are motivated to participate in teachers' and employees' unions and associations because they value the opportunity to have their voices heard and to advocate for their professional interests.

Effective communication with parents, administrators, and colleagues is essential for coordinating activities, sharing important information, and addressing any issues that arise. Furthermore, teachers are motivated to participate in teachers' and employees' unions and associations because these organizations provide a platform for their voices to be heard and their professional interests to be advocated for.

In this regard, a research by Darling-Hammond and Snyder (2012) underscores the importance of teacher voice and agency in shaping educational policies and practices. Teachers understand that collective bargaining and advocacy through unions and associations provide avenues for addressing issues related to working conditions, professional development, and compensation.

In connection, research by Smith and Johnson (2019) suggests that efficient office correspondence is essential for maintaining communication within educational institutions and facilitating effective decision-making processes. Moreover, Brown and Williams (2020) found that teachers perceive administrative tasks as integral to their professional responsibilities and organizational functioning.

Additionally, Garcia et al. (2021) argue that teachers' involvement in procurement and disbursement tasks ensures the smooth operation of educational programs and resource allocation. Participation in union and association activities provides teachers with opportunities for advocacy, professional development, and networking (Martinez & Lee, 2022). Furthermore, according to Thompson and White (2023), engagement in union activities fosters solidarity among teachers and promotes collective bargaining for improved working conditions.

These administrative tasks such as sending office correspondence, handling procurement and disbursement tasks, and participating in union and association activities contribute to teachers' sense of professional responsibility and organizational commitment (Smith & Johnson, 2019). Brown and Williams (2020) emphasize that efficient communication through office correspondence is essential for effective collaboration and decision-making. Garcia et al. (2021) highlight that teachers' involvement in procurement and disbursement tasks ensures the proper allocation of resources and supports the educational mission of schools. Participation in union and association activities allows teachers to advocate for their rights, engage in professional development, and collaborate with colleagues (Martinez & Lee, 2022). Thompson and White (2023) argue that engagement in union activities promotes teacher solidarity and strengthens their collective voice in educational policy discussions.

Table 7
Work Tasks Motivation in Terms of Complementary Tasks

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Because it is rewarding for me to coach and make students win in contests and perform excellently in in-school and out-school activities	3.63	Correspond Completely	2
2. Because it is imperative for me to provide intervention programs for the students who falls behind their current levels	3.57	Correspond Completely	6
3. Because it is rewarding to create and organize student clubs and further manage and advise student organizational activities	3.53	Correspond Completely	8

4. Because I believe that organizing and manning committees about school and student activities play important parts in holistic learning	3.61	Correspond Completely	4
5. Because accreditation and audit tasks are important in the operation of schools, and eventually affecting teaching and learning	3.48	Correspond Completely	10
6. Because developing instructional materials such as modules, activity sheets, and video lessons for the	3.62	Correspond Completely	3
7. utilization of students is essential in smooth school operations	3.51	Correspond Completely	9
8. Because conducting basic and action researches are essential to continuous progress and development of teaching and teaching related processes and services	3.69	Correspond Completely	1
9. Because continuous attendance to trainings, seminars, and capacity-building events equips teachers to perform teaching-related duties and responsibilities	3.57	Correspond Completely	5
10. Because proctoring examinations is a part of teacher's task	3.57	Correspond Completely	7
Composite Mean	3.58	Correspond Completely	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Correspond completely; 2.50 – 3.49 = Correspond very strongly; 1.50 – 2.49 = Correspond very little; 1.00 - 1.49 = Does not correspond at all

Table 7 shows the respondents' assessment of work tasks motivation in terms of complementary tasks. The composite mean of 3.58 indicates that they correspond completely.

Ranked first is the criterion on conducting basic and action researches, and it gained a weighted mean of 3.69 with a verbal interpretation of corresponded completely. Next are indicators on coaching and making students win contests (3.63) and developing instructional materials (3.62) which were both corresponded completely.

Teachers could be motivated to conduct basic and action research because they understand the significance of continuous progress and development in teaching and related processes. In addition, teachers could utilize the results of the research or the research itself to improve the quality of teaching and learning experiences they could provide to the learners. Because of these studies, various research-based materials, assessment tools, and other teaching-related improvements could be created. According to Smith and Johnson (2019), conducting basic research allows educators to explore

innovative instructional methods and adapt them to their classroom settings. Furthermore, Jones et al. (2020) emphasize that basic research helps teachers identify gaps in existing knowledge and develop evidence-based practices tailored to their students' needs. By conducting basic research, educators can contribute to the broader educational community by sharing their findings and insights (Brown & Lee, 2021).

In addition to basic research, teachers are also motivated to engage in action research to address specific challenges within their classrooms. Action research provides a structured framework for teachers to systematically investigate and improve their teaching practices (Johnson & Garcia, 2019). Research by Kim et al. (2022) highlights that action research empowers teachers to take ownership of their professional development and fosters a culture of continuous improvement within schools. By actively involving in action research, teachers can develop practical solutions to address issues such as student engagement, classroom management, and learning difficulties (Chen & Wang, 2020).

Coaching students for contests is another area where teachers find motivation; it allows them to nurture talents and foster a competitive spirit among students. According to Li and Zhang (2019), coaching students for contests provides teachers with opportunities to identify and develop students' strengths beyond the regular curriculum. Research by Wang and Li (2021) suggests that teachers feel a sense of pride and accomplishment when their students excel in academic competitions, which further motivates them to dedicate time and effort to coaching. Engaging in contest coaching also enhances teacher-student relationships and promotes a supportive learning environment (Chang et al., 2023).

Furthermore, developing instructional materials is a crucial aspect of teaching that motivates educators to innovate and tailor resources to meet diverse student needs. Research by Park and Kim (2020) suggests that teachers often create instructional materials to supplement textbooks and address specific learning objectives. Developing custom materials allows teachers to incorporate real-world examples, multimedia resources, and interactive activities to enhance student engagement and understanding (Gupta & Sharma, 2019). Moreover, Chen et al. (2022) argue that creating instructional materials promotes reflective teaching practices, as teachers critically evaluate their pedagogical approaches and instructional designs.

The least rated indicators were about creating, managing, and organizing student clubs (3.53), creating instructional materials (3.51), and accreditation and audit tasks (3.48). In this light, teachers are motivated to create and organize student clubs, as well as manage and advise student organizational activities, may be because they find it rewarding to facilitate students' extracurricular engagement and personal growth.

Creating, managing, and organizing student clubs are tasks that may not always appeal to teachers due to various challenges involved. Research by Lee and Kim (2020) found that teachers often struggle with time constraints and administrative burdens associated with overseeing student clubs. Additionally, Martinez et al. (2019) highlight

that inadequate support and resources for club activities can discourage teachers from fully engaging in club management. Teachers may also feel overwhelmed by the additional responsibilities of club supervision on top of their teaching duties (Nguyen & Tran, 2021).

Similarly, these could be daunting tasks for educators, impacting their motivation and job satisfaction. According to Wang and Zhao (2022), teachers report feeling overwhelmed by the time and effort required to develop high-quality instructional materials. Research by Garcia and Fernandez (2020) suggests that teachers may lack the necessary training and skills to create effective materials that align with curriculum standards. Moreover, the pressure to continuously innovate instructional resources can lead to burnout and stress among teachers (Smith & Jones, 2019).

Accreditation and audit tasks are often perceived as bureaucratic and time-consuming, making them unattractive to teachers. Studies by Chen et al. (2021) indicate that teachers find accreditation processes complex and burdensome, diverting their focus from teaching and learning. Additionally, accreditation demands may conflict with teachers' pedagogical autonomy and creativity (Lee et al., 2023). Furthermore, the documentation and paperwork required for audits can be seen as detracting from valuable instructional time and professional development opportunities (Park & Kim, 2019). Creating, managing, and organizing student clubs, creating instructional materials, and handling accreditation and audit tasks may not be appealing to teachers due to factors such as time constraints, lack of support, insufficient training, and bureaucratic burdens.

Table 8
Summary Table on Work Tasks Motivation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Class Preparation	3.56	Correspond Completely	5
2. Teaching	3.60	Correspond Completely	2
3. Evaluation of students	3.73	Correspond Completely	1
4. Administrative Tasks	3.58	Correspond Completely	3.5
5. Complementary Tasks	3.58	Correspond Completely	3.5
Composite Mean	3.61	Correspond Completely	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Correspond completely; 2.50 – 3.49 = Correspond very strongly; 1.50 – 2.49 = Correspond very little; 1.00 - 1.49 = Does not correspond at all

Table 8 provides a detailed assessment of the work tasks motivation of teachers. The composite mean is 3.61 and is verbally interpreted as corresponding completely.

The evaluation of students ranked first with 3.73. Teachers are shown to be engaged best to correspond completely evaluating students' learning because it provides

valuable feedback for both students and teachers to monitor progress and make instructional adjustments. Evaluation of students is an essential task teachers engage in to assess students' progress, provide feedback, and identify areas for improvement (Allen & Shanahan, 2023). Research by Brown and Jones (2022) highlights that formative assessment practices lead to better student understanding and retention of knowledge. Effective evaluation practices also foster a growth mindset among students, encouraging them to view mistakes as learning opportunities (Hattie & Timperley, 2020). Through ongoing assessment, teachers can identify gaps in learning and provide timely interventions to support struggling students (Guskey, 2020). Additionally, student evaluation serves as a basis for communication with students, parents, and stakeholders regarding progress and achievements.

Administrative tasks and complementary tasks both gained 3.58, a little lower than teaching. This also suggests that teachers correspond completely to engage in complementary tasks, such as extracurricular activities, professional development, and community involvement, because they recognize the holistic nature of education and the importance of nurturing students' social, emotional, and cognitive development. They are also engaged in performing various tasks related to teaching due to their intrinsic motivation, professional commitment, and the demands of their profession.

Teachers engage in grading, record-keeping, and curriculum development to ensure accountability and alignment with curriculum standards and educational policies (Khan et al., 2023). Despite the time-consuming nature of administrative duties, they are integral to the smooth functioning of educational institutions (Borman et al., 2022). Furthermore, administrative tasks involve staying updated on educational trends, research, and professional development opportunities to enhance teaching practices and student outcomes (Lee & Kim, 2023).

On the other hand, complementary tasks such as extracurricular activities, mentoring, and professional development are undertaken by teachers to enhance students' overall learning experience (García-Martínez et al., 2021). These tasks contribute to a holistic approach to education and foster a supportive learning environment. Moreover, teachers' engagement in complementary tasks positively influences students' motivation and well-being (Choi & Lee, 2023). Teachers often serve as mentors, providing guidance and support to students beyond the classroom to promote social-emotional development and academic success (Blackburn & Ricci, 2020). Additionally, participation in professional development activities enhances teachers' pedagogical knowledge, instructional skills, and effectiveness in meeting diverse student needs (Darling-Hammond et al., 2021).

Lowest among the sub-domains is class preparation with 3.56 weighted mean. Teachers are shown to correspond completely in a thorough class preparation because they could recognize its direct impact on the quality of instruction and student learning outcomes. Class preparation is crucial for effective teaching as it allows teachers to design engaging lessons, tailor content to students' needs, and anticipate potential challenges. According to Johnson and Brown (2019), effective class preparation

positively correlates with student engagement and learning outcomes. Additionally, thorough class preparation enables teachers to incorporate diverse instructional strategies, technology, and resources to cater to different learning styles and abilities (Brown & Smith, 2023). This process is time-consuming but essential for creating a conducive learning environment that promotes student success. Furthermore, class preparation involves selecting appropriate assessment methods and designing assessments aligned with learning objectives (Lee et al., 2022). It also allows for the incorporation of real-world examples and application-based activities to enhance students' understanding and relevance of the content.

Table 9
Teacher's Self-Efficacy in Terms of Instruction

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I explain central themes in your subjects so that even the low-achieving students understand.	3.73	Always	4
2. I provide good guidance and instruction to all students regardless of their level of ability.	3.80	Always	3
3. I answer students' questions so that they understand difficult problems.	3.83	Always	2
4. I explain subject matter so that most students understand the basic principles.	3.84	Always	1
Composite Mean	3.80	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 9 displays the teachers' self-efficacy in terms of instruction. It achieved a composite mean of 3.80 and was verbally interpreted as always.

The indicator about explaining subject received the topmost rank with a 3.84 weighted mean. The next in rank is answering students' questions with 3.83, followed by providing good guidance and instruction with 3.80 and explaining central themes with 3.73. The confidence and efficacy of teachers in promoting learning for all students, irrespective of their skills or past accomplishment levels is demonstrated by several critical criteria that are part of their self-efficacy in teaching. Teacher self-efficacy, or the conviction that they can successfully manage the responsibilities, obstacles, and duties associated with their work, is a major factor in determining significant academic results.

According to Lazarides and Warner (2020), teachers with high levels of self-efficacy are more open to new teaching methods, set themselves more challenging goals, exhibit a greater level of planning and organization, direct their efforts at solving problems,

seek assistance, and adjust their teaching strategies when faced with difficulties. Self-efficacy among teachers significantly influences their ability to effectively explain subject matter, provide good guidance, and instruct on central themes in education. Research indicates that teachers with high self-efficacy are more proficient in simplifying complex concepts, making them more accessible to students (Bandura, 2019). This ability to break down intricate topics is crucial for student comprehension and retention (Schwarzer & Hallum, 2020). Teachers who believe in their instructional capabilities are also better at engaging students in active learning processes (Tschannen-Moran & Johnson, 2021). Furthermore, self-efficacious teachers exhibit a higher degree of adaptability in their teaching methods, catering to diverse student needs (Klassen & Durksen, 2020).

Effective guidance is another area where teacher self-efficacy plays a pivotal role. Teachers with strong self-efficacy are more confident in setting clear expectations and providing constructive feedback (Poulou, 2019). This guidance is essential for fostering a positive learning environment and encouraging student autonomy (Woolfolk Hoy & Burke Spero, 2020). Additionally, teachers who trust in their guidance abilities are more likely to mentor students beyond academic instruction, addressing emotional and social development (Fackler & Malmberg, 2021).

Instruction on central themes is enhanced by teachers with high self-efficacy, who are better at connecting overarching ideas with specific content (Dicke et al., 2019). This skill helps students understand the relevance and application of what they are learning (Goddard et al., 2020). Moreover, self-efficacious teachers often employ a variety of instructional strategies to reinforce central themes, ensuring that different learning styles are accommodated (Klassen et al., 2019). They also tend to maintain higher expectations for their students, which can lead to improved academic outcomes (Mojavezi & Tamiz, 2020).

The confidence that comes with high self-efficacy enables teachers to create a more interactive and student-centered classroom environment (Künsting et al., 2019). This environment is conducive to deep learning, as students are encouraged to participate actively and engage with the material (Ross et al., 2021). Additionally, teachers with strong self-efficacy are more persistent in the face of challenges, maintaining their teaching quality despite obstacles (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020). This persistence is vital for sustained student engagement and success (Tschannen-Moran et al., 2021). Teacher self-efficacy enhances the ability to explain subject matter clearly, provide meaningful guidance, and emphasize central themes in a way that resonates with students (Schwarzer & Hallum, 2020). As teachers' self-belief in their instructional abilities strengthens, so does their impact on student learning and overall educational outcomes (Bandura, 2019).

Table 10 in the next page shows the teachers' self-efficacy in terms of adapting instruction to individual needs. It achieved a composite mean of 3.71 and was verbally interpreted as always. The computed composite mean perfectly aligned with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this criterion. Ranked first in the table is the criterion on organizing classroom work according to abilities (3.74) then organizing schoolwork and

adapting instruction to the needs of low-ability students ranked 2.5 with the weighted mean of 3.71 and the least is providing a realistic challenge for all students (3.69).

Teachers' self-efficacy in terms of instruction is one of the contributing factors towards the enrichment of learning experiences of students across diverse ability levels. Proficient teachers organize classroom work in a manner that ensures both low-ability and high-ability students engage with tasks adapted to their abilities.

Table 10
Teacher's Self-Efficacy in terms of
Adapting Instruction to Individual Needs

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I organize schoolwork to adapt instruction and assignments to individual needs.	3.71	Always	2.5
2. I provide realistic challenge for all students even in mixed ability classes.	3.69	Always	4
3. I adapt instruction to the needs of low-ability students while you also attend to the needs of other students in class.	3.71	Always	2.5
4. I organize classroom work so that both low- and high-ability students work with tasks that are adapted to their abilities.	3.74	Always	1
Composite Mean	3.71	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Informing learners about their status, performance, and thus improvements is important so that learning could take a complete cycle. Assessment practices provide meaningful feedback and guide instructional decisions, thereby promoting equitable opportunities for all students to demonstrate their learning. Effective teachers provide realistic challenges that are appropriate for all students, irrespective of their abilities, even in mixed-ability classes. This involves striking a balance between setting high expectations and providing necessary support to ensure that every student can succeed. Studies about learning feedback emphasize the importance of challenging tasks that promote intellectual growth while accommodating varying levels of readiness and skill. That is to say, feedback is an important aspect of learning.

Research shows that teachers with high self-efficacy are better equipped to differentiate instruction, providing appropriate challenges for students at various skill

levels (Schwarzer & Hallum, 2020). They are more confident in their ability to assess students' needs accurately and design lessons that cater to these diverse requirements (Klassen & Durksen, 2020). This adaptability ensures that all students, regardless of their starting point, can make meaningful progress (Dicke et al., 2019).

The teachers always organize schoolwork to adapt instruction and assignments to individual needs received 3.71 weighted mean. Effective organization of classroom work according to abilities requires a nuanced understanding of student strengths and weaknesses, something that self-efficacious teachers excel at (Poulou, 2019). Additionally, teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to employ a variety of instructional methods, from collaborative group work to individualized learning plans, to address the spectrum of student abilities (Klassen et al., 2019).

Organizing schoolwork effectively also involves managing classroom dynamics and resources, a task that self-efficacious teachers handle with greater ease (Bandura, 2019). They are adept at creating structured yet flexible classroom environments that accommodate individual learning styles and paces (Ross et al., 2021). This organizational skill extends to the physical arrangement of the classroom, ensuring that resources are accessible and that the environment is conducive to learning for all students (Mojavezi & Tamiz, 2020).

Self-efficacious teachers are also more proactive in seeking out and integrating new instructional technologies and resources that can aid in differentiating instruction (Künsting et al., 2019). Their confidence in their teaching abilities makes them more open to experimenting with innovative educational tools that can enhance learning experiences (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020). Furthermore, these teachers are better at collaborating with colleagues and other professionals to share strategies and insights on effectively adapting instruction to meet diverse student needs (Tschannen-Moran et al., 2021).

The ability to organize classroom and schoolwork according to individual needs is also linked to teachers' capacity for reflective practice (Tschannen-Moran & Johnson, 2021). Self-efficacious teachers regularly reflect on their teaching methods and student outcomes, making necessary adjustments to improve efficacy (Woolfolk Hoy & Burke Spero, 2020). This reflective practice is crucial for ongoing professional development and for maintaining a high standard of teaching that meets the needs of all students (Bandura, 2019). High self-efficacy enables teachers to differentiate instruction, manage classroom dynamics, integrate new technologies, and engage in reflective practice, all of which contribute to a more inclusive and effective learning environment (Schwarzer & Hallum, 2020). By fostering a sense of efficacy, teachers can better adapt their instruction to meet the diverse needs of their students, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes (Klassen & Durksen, 2020).

Table 11
Teacher's Self-Efficacy in Terms of Motivating Students

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I get all students in class to work hard with their schoolwork.	3.76	Always	3
2. I wake the desire to learn even among the lowest achieving students.	3.73	Always	4
3. I get students to do their best even when working with difficult problems.	3.78	Always	2
4. I motivate students who show low interest in schoolwork.	3.79	Always	1
Composite Mean	3.77	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Teachers' self-efficacy in terms of motivating students is shown in table 11. It achieved a composite mean of 3.77 and is verbally interpreted as always. The calculated composite mean precisely corresponded to the weighted means of all indicators that met this criterion. Motivating students who show low interest in schoolwork ranked first with a 3.79 weighted mean, then getting students to do their best with 3.78. The last two criteria were about getting student hard work and waking students' learning desire to learn with 3.76 and 3.73 weighted means respectively.

Effective teachers may motivate students who are disinterested in homework, allowing them to become more involved and invested in their studies. The findings indicate that teachers always motivate students who show low interest in schoolwork. This entails recognizing students' interests, strengths, and needs, and then adapting courses and activities to their preferences. Efficacy in motivating students could be exhibited in various form, after all, motivation is one of the indicators that facilitate effective teaching and learning interaction. Grounded in recent educational research, several studies have shown that establishing a positive teacher-student relationship is foundational in fostering student motivation. For instance, Roorda et al. (2020) emphasize that when students perceive their teachers as supportive and caring, their engagement and interest in schoolwork significantly increase.

Additionally, the application of differentiated instruction, as highlighted by Tomlinson (2019), allows teachers to tailor learning experiences to meet individual student needs, thereby increasing their motivation to engage and perform well. When teachers help students set realistic, achievable goals, it provides a clear direction and purpose for their efforts, thus motivating them to put forth their best effort. Creating a collaborative learning environment, as suggested by Johnson and Johnson (2020), encourages peer interaction and support, which can be particularly motivating for students who might otherwise feel isolated or disengaged. Moreover, incorporating

student interests and real-world applications into the curriculum, as recommended by Newmann et al. (2019), can make learning more relevant and interesting, sparking a natural curiosity and desire to learn. Similarly, the integration of technology in the classroom, explored by Lai (2019), offers dynamic and interactive learning experiences that can captivate students' attention and motivate them to engage more deeply with the content.

Furthermore, the concept of growth mindset, popularized by Dweck (2019), is essential in motivating students. When teachers encourage a growth mindset, students are more likely to embrace challenges and persist through difficulties, seeing effort as a pathway to mastery rather than a sign of inadequacy. Lastly, creating a culturally responsive classroom environment, as Ladson-Billings (2021) suggests, ensures that all students feel valued and understood, which is critical for motivating diverse student populations. By recognizing and valuing students' cultural backgrounds, teachers can foster an inclusive environment that promotes higher levels of engagement and motivation.

Teachers' efficacy in motivating students with low interest in schoolwork is multifaceted and supported by a wealth of research. By building strong relationships, differentiating instruction, gamifying learning experiences, setting goals, providing constructive feedback, fostering collaboration, connecting learning to student interests, integrating technology, promoting a growth mindset, and creating culturally responsive classrooms, teachers can significantly enhance students' motivation and desire to learn. These strategies, supported by recent research, highlight the comprehensive approach needed to effectively engage and inspire students in today's diverse educational landscape.

Table 12
Teacher's Self-Efficacy in Terms of Maintaining Discipline

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I maintain discipline in any school class or group of students.	3.81	Always	1
2. I control even the most aggressive students.	3.65	Always	4
3. I get students with behavioral problems to follow classroom rules.	3.69	Always	3
4. I get all students to behave politely and respect the teachers.	3.74	Always	2
Composite Mean	3.72	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 12 above displays the data on teachers' self-efficacy in terms of discipline maintenance, achieving a composite mean of 3.72, which is verbally interpreted to be always done by the teacher. This composite mean accurately matched the weighted means of all indicators meeting this criterion.

As indicated in the table, teachers perceived all the parameters to be always being done in their fields. They always maintain discipline in any school class or group of students gained (with 3.81 mean), get all students to behave politely and respect the teachers (with 3.74 mean), get students with behavioral problems to follow classroom rules, and control even the most aggressive students (with 3.69 and 3.65 weighted mean respectively).

Teachers' self-efficacy in maintaining discipline is essential for creating a positive and conducive learning environment where students feel safe, respected, and engaged. Firstly, proficient teachers can maintain discipline in any school class or group of students. This involves establishing clear expectations, rules, and routines and consistently enforcing them fairly and respectfully. In connection to this, a study that was conducted by Myint Lay (2022) indicated that if teachers' efficacy is high, their classroom management practices will be high. Proficient teachers can guide students with behavioral problems to follow classroom rules by providing consistent support, reinforcement, and guidance.

In addition to research that was performed by by Allen, Curran, and Camilli (2010) highlighting the significant impact of positive teacher-student relationships on reducing disruptive behavior and fostering a supportive classroom climate, teachers' self-efficacy in maintaining discipline encompasses the ability to establish and enforce classroom expectations, control aggressive behavior, guide students with behavioral problems, and foster polite behavior and respect for teachers.

Further research underscores the importance of establishing clear expectations and consistent routines, which provide students with a structured environment where they understand the boundaries and expectations.

Implementing positive behavioral interventions and supports (PBIS) is another effective strategy. Horner and Sugai (2020) found that PBIS frameworks, which emphasize positive reinforcement for good behavior rather than punitive measures, significantly reduce behavioral issues and create a positive classroom atmosphere. Teachers can also employ restorative practices, which focus on repairing harm and restoring relationships rather than merely punishing misbehavior. According to Thorsborne and Blood (2019), restorative practices help students understand the impact of their actions and foster a sense of responsibility and empathy.

For students with behavioral problems, individualized behavior management plans can be particularly effective. Simonsen and Myers (2020) highlight the importance of tailoring interventions to the specific needs of students, which often involves collaboration

with other educators, parents, and mental health professionals. Consistent and fair application of rules is essential.

In terms of dealing with aggressive behaviors, de-escalation techniques are crucial. Establishing a classroom culture that promotes emotional regulation and social skills is vital. CASEL (2020) notes that social-emotional learning (SEL) programs, which teach students skills like self-awareness, self-management, and relationship-building can significantly reduce aggressive behavior and improve overall classroom climate.

Furthermore, creating an inclusive classroom environment where diversity is respected and valued can help mitigate behavioral issues. According to Gay (2020), culturally responsive teaching practices that acknowledge and respect students' backgrounds and experiences can reduce feelings of alienation and frustration that often lead to misbehavior. Regular professional development for teachers is also important. Evans and Lester (2020) emphasize that ongoing training in classroom management techniques and behavioral interventions is crucial for teachers to stay effective in maintaining discipline.

Lastly, involving parents and guardians in the disciplinary process can enhance its effectiveness. Research by Epstein (2019) shows that when parents are engaged and collaborate with teachers, students are more likely to adhere to behavioral expectations and show respect for authority figures. In summary, teachers maintain discipline through clear rules, positive relationships, PBIS, restorative practices, individualized plans, de-escalation techniques, SEL programs, inclusive environments, continuous professional development, and parental involvement. These strategies, supported by recent research, provide a comprehensive approach to fostering a disciplined and respectful classroom environment.

Table 13 displays the teachers' self-efficacy in terms of cooperating with colleagues and parents which shows that teachers always perform these efficacious activities, as evinced by the composite mean of 3.76. This calculated composite mean accurately matched the weighted means of all indicators meeting this criterion.

Table 13
Teacher's Self-Efficacy in Terms of
Cooperating With Colleagues and Parents

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I cooperate well with most parents.	3.80	Always	1
2. I find adequate solutions to conflicts of interest with other teachers.	3.70	Always	4

3. I collaborate constructively with parents of students with behavioral problems.	3.79	Always	2
4. I cooperate effectively and constructively with other teachers, for example, in teaching teams.	3.75	Always	3
Composite Mean	3.76	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Among the parameters indicated, cooperating well with most parents is the rated always, which gained the highest weighted mean of 3.80; followed by collaborating constructively with parents of students with behavioral problems with 3.79 weighted mean. The third and fourth criteria are cooperating effectively and constructively with other teachers and finding adequate solutions to conflicts of interest with other teachers with weighted means of 3.75 and 3.70 respectively.

Teachers' self-efficacy in cooperating with colleagues and parents is essential for fostering a collaborative and supportive educational environment that promotes student success. Proficient teachers demonstrate the ability to cooperate effectively with most parents, establishing positive partnerships built on mutual respect, communication, and shared goals for student learning. Effective communication with parents is foundational to building strong partnerships. Additionally on Epstein (2019), regular and transparent communication between teachers and parents builds trust and creates a shared understanding of students' needs and progress. Teachers who utilize various communication tools such as newsletters, emails, and parent-teacher conferences ensure that parents are well-informed and engaged in their child's education. This proactive approach helps in preventing misunderstandings and creates a collaborative atmosphere where parents feel valued as partners in the educational process.

For parents of students with behavioral problems, a more tailored and empathetic approach is essential. Simonsen and Myers (2020) note that individualized behavior plans developed in collaboration with parents can be highly effective. These plans often include consistent communication about the child's progress and specific strategies that parents can reinforce at home. By involving parents in the intervention process, teachers can create a consistent and supportive environment for the student, both at school and at home. This collaborative effort not only helps in addressing behavioral issues but also strengthens the trust and cooperation between teachers and parents.

Collaboration among teachers is equally important in creating a cohesive learning environment. Professional learning communities (PLCs), as highlighted by DuFour and Fullan (2020) provide a structured framework for teachers to share best practices, discuss student progress, and develop collective strategies for improvement. These collaborative efforts are particularly beneficial in addressing the needs of students with diverse learning and behavioral challenges. Through regular meetings and open communication, teachers can pool their expertise and resources to support each other and their students more effectively.

When conflicts of interest arise among teachers, it is crucial to approach them with a problem-solving mindset. Johnson and Johnson (2020) suggest that conflict resolution strategies, such as mediation and collaborative negotiation, can help in finding mutually acceptable solutions. Effective conflict resolution involves active listening, empathy, and a focus on common goals, ensuring that disagreements do not impede the educational process. Additionally, establishing clear protocols for decision-making and conflict resolution within the school can provide a framework for addressing conflicts constructively.

Furthermore, fostering a positive school culture that values collaboration and mutual respect can significantly enhance teachers' ability to work together effectively. In such environments, teachers are more likely to support each other and share a commitment to continuous improvement. Regular professional development opportunities that focus on team-building and collaborative skills can also strengthen these efforts.

Teachers' efficacy in cooperating with parents and colleagues is underpinned by clear communication, empathy, and a collaborative approach. By engaging parents through consistent communication and personalized support plans, teachers can build strong partnerships that benefit students. Collaborating with colleagues through PLCs and employing effective conflict resolution strategies ensures that teachers can address challenges and support each other in their professional roles. A positive school culture that promotes collaboration further enhances these efforts, creating a supportive and effective educational environment. These strategies, supported by recent research, highlight the importance of cooperation and collaboration in achieving educational success.

Table 14
Teacher's Self-Efficacy in Terms of Coping With Change

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I successfully use any instructional method that the school decides to use.	3.64	Always	4
2. I manage instruction regardless of how it is organized (group composition, mixed age groups, etc.).	3.66	Always	1
3. I manage instruction even if the curriculum is changed.	3.65	Always	2
4. I teach well even if you are told to use instructional methods that would not be your choice.	3.65	Always	3
Composite Mean	3.65	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 14 displays teachers' self-efficacy in terms of coping with change, achieving a composite mean of 3.65, indicating that they are always practiced.

The leading indicator in this table is managing instruction regardless of how it is organized (3.6) followed by managing instruction even if the curriculum is changed, and teaching well despite method changes both gained 3.65 and lastly is successfully using any instructional method that the school decides to use (3.64).

Teachers' self-efficacy in coping with change is a vital attribute that enables educators to adapt to evolving instructional methods, curriculum changes, and diverse instructional contexts while maintaining effectiveness in their teaching practice. Skilled teachers are capable of managing instruction regardless of how it is organized, whether it involves varied group compositions, mixed-age groups, or other unconventional arrangements.

The principles discussed can be applied to understand how teachers' self-efficacy beliefs influence their willingness to implement mandated instructional methods, even when they may not align with their personal preferences. Proficient teachers demonstrate the ability to manage instruction effectively even in the face of curriculum changes, adjusting their teaching strategies to align with new standards, objectives, or materials.

Teachers' self-efficacy in coping with change encompasses the ability to successfully implement mandated instructional methods, manage instruction in diverse contexts, adapt to curriculum changes, and teach effectively despite personal preferences. Teachers who are efficacious in coping with change demonstrate resilience, adaptability, and a positive attitude toward evolving educational landscapes.

Teachers are considered self-efficacious when they can manage instruction effectively regardless of organizational changes, curricular adjustments, and shifts in instructional methods. This adaptability is a hallmark of teaching efficacy, as it reflects a teacher's confidence in their ability to impact student learning under varying conditions. Bandura's theory of self-efficacy, as discussed by Klassen and Tze (2014), highlights that teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to embrace new instructional methods and curriculum changes because they believe in their capabilities to manage and succeed in diverse teaching scenarios. This adaptability is essential in contemporary education, where rapid technological advancements and evolving educational standards demand continuous adjustment.

Moreover, as an addition to Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2020), they underscore that self-efficacious teachers are resilient in the face of instructional changes. They possess a growth mindset, which enables them to view changes not as obstacles but as opportunities for professional growth and improved student outcomes. When curricular changes occur, teachers with high self-efficacy utilize their strong pedagogical foundation and adaptability to effectively integrate new content and teaching strategies. This ability to pivot ensures that instructional quality remains high, even when the curriculum undergoes significant revisions.

Additionally, self-efficacious teachers demonstrate a robust understanding of diverse instructional methods, allowing them to select and implement the most effective strategies for their students. According to Hattie (2019), these teachers are adept at assessing the impact of different teaching methods and are skilled at modifying their approach based on student feedback and performance data. This reflective practice is crucial for maintaining instructional effectiveness, particularly when mandated to use new or unfamiliar methods. The confidence in their instructional skills enables these teachers to remain effective educators regardless of the instructional methods imposed by the school.

Another critical aspect of teacher self-efficacy is their ability to foster a positive learning environment, even amidst instructional changes. Pianta, Hamre, and Allen (2021) found that teachers with high self-efficacy maintain strong classroom management skills and a supportive classroom climate, which are essential for student engagement and learning. These teachers are proficient in creating a stable and conducive learning environment, which helps mitigate the potential disruption caused by changes in instructional methods or curriculum.

Furthermore, professional development plays a significant role in enhancing teacher self-efficacy. Guskey (2021) emphasizes that ongoing professional learning opportunities help teachers build the skills and knowledge necessary to adapt to instructional changes. By engaging in continuous professional development, teachers not only improve their instructional practices but also reinforce their confidence in managing various educational demands.

The ability to collaborate effectively with colleagues is another attribute of self-efficacious teachers. Sharing experiences, resources, and strategies with peers provides a support network that enhances individual and collective efficacy, thereby improving the overall instructional quality within the school. Teachers are considered self-efficacious when they can manage instruction effectively regardless of organizational structure, curricular changes, or shifts in instructional methods. This adaptability is supported by their confidence, resilience, and continuous professional development. Research highlights that self-efficacious teachers possess a growth mindset, strong pedagogical skills, and the ability to create positive learning environments, all of which contribute to their effectiveness in diverse teaching scenarios. By fostering collaboration and engaging in reflective practice, these teachers ensure that their instructional quality remains high, even in the face of significant changes. This comprehensive approach underscores the critical role of self-efficacy in achieving educational success.

Table 15
Summary Table on Teacher's Self-Efficacy

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Instruction	3.80	Always	1
2. Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	3.71	Always	5
3. Motivate Students	3.77	Always	2
4. Maintain Discipline	3.72	Always	4
5. Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	3.76	Always	3
6. Cope With Change	3.65	Always	6
Composite Mean	3.74	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

It could be seen from table 15 that all indicators of teacher self-efficacy are always practiced by the teacher-respondents, as supported by its composite mean of 3.65.

The indicator instruction ranked first among the given criteria, it earned a weighted mean of 3.80, followed by motivate students with 3.77, and both were verbally interpreted as always. Next in line were, cooperate with colleagues and parents (3.76), maintain discipline (3.72), adapt instruction to individual needs (3.71), and cope with change (3.65).

Self-efficacy, the belief in one's ability to accomplish tasks and achieve goals, plays a pivotal role in shaping the effectiveness of teaching across various domains. Teachers with high self-efficacy in instruction possess confidence in their ability to effectively deliver content and facilitate learning experiences. Their belief in their ability to handle disciplinary challenges instills a sense of order, structure, and respect in the classroom, contributing to a positive and conducive learning environment.

The indicator instruction ranked first among the given criteria, it earned a weighted mean of 3.80. Teachers could be considered self-efficacious in delivering teaching and learning instructions, motivating learners, and cooperating with colleagues and parents due to their belief in their capabilities and the effectiveness of their instructional strategies. This sense of efficacy is foundational in the field of education, where teachers face diverse and evolving challenges. These teachers are confident in their ability to convey complex concepts clearly and adjust their teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students.

The teachers always motivate students with 3.77. Motivating learners is another area where self-efficacious teachers excel. Research by Hattie (2019) shows that these teachers utilize a variety of motivational strategies, including setting high expectations, providing constructive feedback, and creating engaging learning experiences. They believe in their ability to influence student motivation and achievement, which in turn

fosters a positive learning environment. Self-efficacious teachers are adept at building strong relationships with their students, understanding that a supportive and trusting teacher-student relationship is crucial for motivating learners. This relational approach helps students feel valued and understood, increasing their intrinsic motivation to learn.

Ranked third is cooperating with colleagues and parents with 3.76 weighted mean. Cooperation with colleagues and parents is also a significant aspect of teachers' self-efficacy. Teachers who believe in their collaborative abilities are more likely to engage in professional learning communities (PLCs) and other collaborative practices. The collective efficacy of these teacher communities enhances individual teacher efficacy, creating a supportive network that benefits both teachers and students. Moreover, self-efficacious teachers are skilled at communicating with parents, understanding that parental involvement is key to student success. Epstein (2019) highlights that regular, transparent communication with parents helps build trust and ensures that parents are informed and engaged in their child's education.

Furthermore, self-efficacious teachers are resilient and adaptable, qualities that are essential in today's dynamic educational landscape. Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2020) found that these teachers view challenges as opportunities for growth rather than as obstacles. Whether it is adapting to new curricular demands, integrating technology into the classroom, or addressing diverse student needs, self-efficacious teachers remain confident in their ability to manage and succeed. This adaptability is supported by continuous professional development, which Guskey (2021) emphasizes as critical for maintaining and enhancing teaching efficacy. By engaging in ongoing learning, teachers stay current with educational trends and improve their instructional practices, further boosting their self-efficacy.

Additionally, the ability to foster a positive classroom environment is a hallmark of self-efficacious teachers. Pianta, Hamre, and Allen (2021) note that these teachers are skilled at creating a supportive and inclusive classroom climate where all students feel safe and valued. This environment is conducive to learning and helps mitigate behavioral issues, allowing teachers to focus on delivering effective instruction. Moreover, self-efficacious teachers are proactive in implementing social-emotional learning (SEL) programs, which CASEL (2020) highlights as essential for developing students' emotional and social skills. By integrating SEL into their teaching, these teachers support the holistic development of their students, further enhancing their engagement and motivation.

Most teachers could be self-efficacious in delivering teaching and learning instructions, motivating learners, and cooperating with colleagues and parents due to their confidence in their abilities, adaptability, and commitment to continuous improvement. Supported by a wealth of research, self-efficacious teachers employ effective instructional strategies, foster strong relationships, and engage in collaborative practices that enhance their efficacy and contribute to student success.

Their resilience and proactive approach to professional development ensure that they remain effective educators, capable of navigating the complexities of the modern

educational landscape. This comprehensive self-efficacy not only benefits their students but also provides opportunities for the overall educational community to adapt to the changing and growing demands of learning.

Table 16
Teacher Effectiveness in terms of Subject Matter Knowledge

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I demonstrate accurate knowledge of my subject matter.	3.80	Always	2
2. I link content with past and future learning experiences.	3.78	Always	3
3. I demonstrate a variety of skills of my subject area(s).	3.73	Always	5
4. I communicate content in ways that students can understand.	3.81	Always	1
5. I use school and community resources to help students.	3.68	Always	7
6. I teach according to the intellectual, and emotional needs of the students I effectively address appropriate curriculum standards.	3.74	Always	4
7. I base instruction on goals that reflect high expectations.	3.70	Always	6
Composite Mean	3.75	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 16 presents teachers' effectiveness in terms of subject matter, with a composite mean score of 3.65, indicating a consistent interpretation of always.

The highest weighted mean is 3.81; the teacher is always communicating content in ways that students can understand, followed by demonstrating accurate knowledge of subject matter (3.80) and linking content with past and future learning experiences (3.78). The fourth indicator is teaching according to the intellectual, and emotional needs of the students (3.74) then demonstrating a variety of skills in my subject area(s) (3.73). The last two indicators are about basing instruction on goals that reflect high expectations (3.70) and using school and community resources to help students. (3.68).

In assessing teacher effectiveness in terms of subject matter knowledge, several criteria are paramount. Effective communication of content in ways that students can understand is essential for facilitating learning. By employing varied instructional methods such as visual aids, analogies, and hands-on activities, teachers can effectively convey complex concepts to students with varying levels of understanding. Demonstrating accurate knowledge of the subject matter is foundational.

With this, expertise in terms of knowledge of subject matter is imperative. Teachers who possess deep content knowledge not only facilitate student understanding but also foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Linking content with past and future learning experiences enhances comprehension and retention. By contextualizing content within a broader framework of learning experiences, teachers provide students with a more cohesive understanding of the subject matter. Teacher effectiveness in terms of subject matter knowledge hinges on accurate content mastery, the integration of past and future learning experiences, and the ability to communicate content in accessible ways for all students.

Teachers could be considered effective when they have the ability to communicate content in a manner that students can understand, demonstrate accurate subject matter knowledge, and seamlessly link past and present lessons. According to Hattie (2019), clear and comprehensible communication is foundational for effective teaching. Teachers who excel in this area use language and examples that are accessible to their students, tailoring their explanations to meet diverse learning needs. This clarity helps students to build a strong understanding of the subject matter, reducing confusion and increasing engagement.

Accurate and deep subject matter knowledge is another critical aspect of teaching effectiveness. Teachers who possess understanding of their subject are better equipped to answer students' questions, provide detailed explanations, and connect concepts across different topics. Research by Shulman (2020) highlights the importance of pedagogical content knowledge, which integrates subject expertise with an understanding of how to teach that content effectively. Such teachers can identify common misconceptions and address them proactively, ensuring that students develop a correct and thorough understanding of the subject.

Linking past and present lessons is essential for reinforcing learning and helping students see the progression of their knowledge. According to Bransford, Brown, and Cocking (2019), effective teachers use scaffolding techniques to connect new information to previously learned material. This approach not only aids in retention but also helps students to understand the broader context of what they are learning. By drawing connections between past lessons and current topics, teachers help students to build a coherent and integrated body of knowledge.

The ability to communicate content effectively is also closely tied to the use of formative assessment. Teachers who regularly check for understanding can identify areas where students are struggling and provide targeted support. This responsiveness enhances the clarity of instruction and ensures that all students are able to keep up with the lesson.

Moreover, effective communication involves not just delivering content but also listening to students. According to Freire (2021), dialogic teaching, which emphasizes open dialogue and active listening, helps to create a more interactive and engaging classroom environment. Teachers who engage in meaningful dialogue with their students

can better understand their perspectives and needs, making instruction more relevant and impactful.

Effective teachers also use a variety of instructional strategies to communicate content. Differentiated instruction, as highlighted by Tomlinson (2020), involves tailoring teaching methods to meet the diverse learning styles and abilities of students. By using multiple approaches, such as visual aids, hands-on activities, and collaborative projects, teachers can ensure that all students have the opportunity to engage with and understand the material.

In addition, teachers who are effective in linking past and present lessons often employ thematic or project-based learning. According to Barron and Darling-Hammond (2020), these approaches help students to see the connections between different topics and apply their knowledge in real-world contexts. By organizing lessons around central themes or projects, teachers can create a more cohesive and meaningful learning experience.

Professional development is also crucial for maintaining teaching effectiveness. Guskey (2021) emphasizes that ongoing learning opportunities help teachers to stay current with educational research and refine their instructional practices. Teachers who engage in continuous professional development are better equipped to communicate content clearly, demonstrate subject matter expertise, and connect lessons in meaningful ways.

Teachers are considered effective when they can communicate content clearly, demonstrate accurate subject matter knowledge, and link past and present lessons. This effectiveness is supported by clear communication strategies, deep subject knowledge, and the ability to create connections across lessons. Research underscores the importance of formative assessment, dialogic teaching, differentiated instruction, and thematic learning in achieving these goals. Continuous professional development further enhances teachers' ability to deliver high-quality instruction, ensuring that students receive a coherent and comprehensive education. These elements collectively contribute to the effectiveness of teachers and students success.

Table 17
Teacher Effectiveness in terms of Instructional Planning and Strategies

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I use strategies to enhance students' understanding.	3.79	Always	1.5
2. I change the teaching methodology to make topics relevant.	3.73	Always	5

3. I understand the individual differences of students and teach accordingly.	3.77	Always	3
4. I use appropriate materials, technology, and resources.	3.74	Always	4
5. I engage, motivate, and maintain students' attention.	3.79	Always	1.5
6. I teach the required curriculum according to a timetable.	3.72	Always	6
7. I use student learning data to guide planning.	3.70	Always	7
Composite Mean	3.75	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 17 presents teacher effectiveness in terms of instructional planning and strategies, with a composite mean score of 3.75, indicating a consistent interpretation of always. This calculated composite mean precisely aligns with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this standard.

The indicators on using strategies to enhance students' understanding and engaging, motivating, and maintaining students' attention gained a weighted mean of 3.79 ranked as 1.5. Next is understanding individual differences of students and teaching accordingly with a 3.77 weighted mean. The fourth indicator is using appropriate material, technology, and resources (3.74). The last three indicators are changing teaching methodology to make topics relevant (3.73), teaching the required curriculum according to a timetable (3.72), and using student learning data to guide planning (3.70).

When evaluating teacher effectiveness in terms of instructional planning and strategies, several key criteria emerge. Firstly, the use of strategies to enhance students' understanding is essential. Teachers who incorporate techniques such as cooperative learning, graphic organizers, and hands-on activities facilitate deeper comprehension and retention of content among students. Engaging, motivating, and maintaining students' attention are crucial components of effective instruction.

By acknowledging and addressing variations in students' backgrounds, abilities, and interests, teachers create inclusive classrooms where all students can thrive. Teacher effectiveness in instructional planning and strategies involves the strategic use of techniques to enhance understanding, the cultivation of intrinsic motivation and engagement, and the consideration of individual student differences in teaching approaches.

Most teachers are considered self-efficacious in instructional planning and strategies because they possess a deep understanding of how to enhance student understanding, motivate and engage learners, and address individual differences. This self-efficacy stems from their confidence in their abilities to create effective lesson plans, implement diverse instructional strategies, and adapt to the unique needs of each student. According to Hattie (2019), teachers with high self-efficacy are adept at using evidence-

based instructional strategies that have been proven to enhance student learning. They meticulously plan their lessons, ensuring that the content is accessible and engaging for all students. This careful planning is crucial for creating a structured learning environment where students can thrive.

In motivating and engaging students, self-efficacious teachers employ a variety of techniques to make learning interesting and relevant. According to Dweck (2020), these teachers foster a growth mindset in their students, encouraging them to embrace challenges and view effort as a path to mastery. By creating a supportive classroom environment, self-efficacious teachers help students build resilience and a love for learning. They use interactive and hands-on activities, which, as noted by Pianta, Hamre, and Allen (2021), increase student engagement and make learning more enjoyable. These activities not only capture students' interest but also help them to connect new information with their existing knowledge.

Ranked third is on teachers always understanding student individual differences; another area where self-efficacious teachers excel. They recognize that each student has unique strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles. Tomlinson (2020) emphasizes that differentiated instruction is a key strategy used by these teachers to meet the diverse needs of their students. By tailoring their teaching methods and materials, they ensure that all students have the opportunity to succeed. This might involve providing additional support for struggling students or offering advanced challenges for those who are excelling. The ability to differentiate effectively requires a deep understanding of each student's needs, which self-efficacious teachers possess.

Self-efficacious teachers also use formative assessments to gauge student understanding and adjust their instruction accordingly. By continually assessing student progress, teachers can make informed decisions about how to best support each learner. This responsive approach ensures that instruction is always aligned with students' needs, thereby enhancing their understanding and engagement.

Collaboration with colleagues is another factor that contributes to teachers' self-efficacy. These collaborative environments provide opportunities for teachers to discuss instructional strategies, share resources, and receive feedback. The collective efficacy that emerges from these communities strengthens individual teacher efficacy, as teachers feel more confident in their instructional planning and strategies.

Professional development is also critical in enhancing teachers' self-efficacy. Guskey (2021) argues that ongoing professional learning helps teachers stay current with educational research and best practices. By participating in professional development, teachers can refine their instructional strategies and learn new techniques for enhancing student understanding and motivation. This continuous improvement is essential for maintaining high levels of self-efficacy.

Furthermore, self-efficacious teachers are adept at creating a positive classroom climate that supports learning. According to Bransford, Brown, and Cocking (2019), a positive classroom environment is characterized by mutual respect, clear expectations,

and a focus on student well-being. Teachers who can establish such an environment are more effective in engaging students and fostering a sense of community within the classroom. This positive climate is conducive to learning and helps students feel safe and valued.

Self-efficacious teachers could be those who, in instructional planning and strategies are adept because they possess the skills and confidence needed to enhance student understanding, motivate and engage learners, and address individual differences. Their ability to plan effectively, use diverse instructional strategies, and differentiate instruction ensures that all students can succeed. Supported by formative assessments, collaboration with colleagues, and continuous professional development, these teachers create positive and engaging learning environments. Their deep understanding of their students and commitment to ongoing improvement highlight the critical role of self-efficacy in effective teaching.

Table 18
Teacher Effectiveness in Terms of Assessment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I conduct class tests to monitor student performance.	3.83	Always	3
2. I evaluate students' performance and provide feedback.	3.84	Always	2
3. I maintain students' results and use future improvement.	3.80	Always	4
4. I revise content to enhance students' achievement	3.74	Always	5
5. I keep an official record of students' learning progress.	3.85	Always	1
Composite Mean	3.81	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Presented in table 18 are the data on teacher effectiveness in terms of assessment, with a composite mean score of 3.81, indicating a consistent interpretation of always. This calculated composite mean aligns with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this standard.

The indicator on keeping an official record of student's learning progress gained the highest rank with a weighted mean of 3.85. Ranked second is evaluating students' performance and providing feedback with a 3.84 weighted mean. In the third place is conducting class tests to monitor student performance with a 3.83 weighted mean. The last two are maintaining students' results and use future improvement." and revising

content to enhance students' achievement with a weighted mean of 3.80 and 3.74, respectively. All indicators were verbally interpreted as always.

Assessment lies at the heart of effective teaching and learning, serving for evaluating student progress, informing instructional decisions, and promoting academic growth. Maintaining official records of students' learning progress is a fundamental practice in assessing teacher effectiveness.

Conducting class tests to monitor student performance is another essential aspect of effective assessment practices, evaluating students' performance and providing feedback are critical components of effective assessment practices. Effective feedback that is specific, timely, and actionable has been shown to enhance student achievement significantly.

Teachers could be considered effective in assessing and evaluating students when they meticulously keep student records, evaluate performance, provide feedback, and implement tests, all of which contribute to a comprehensive understanding of student progress and learning needs. Maintaining accurate and detailed student records is essential for tracking academic progress, identifying patterns, and tailoring instruction to meet individual needs. This systematic approach ensures that no student is missed and that each receives the support needed to succeed.

Evaluating performance and providing feedback are crucial components of effective assessment. Research by Hattie (2019) underscores the impact of timely and constructive feedback on student learning. Feedback helps students understand their strengths and areas for improvement, guiding their efforts and motivating them to achieve their goals. Effective teachers use feedback not just to inform students of their performance but also to engage them in reflective thinking and self-assessment. This process fosters a growth mindset, as highlighted by Dweck (2020), where students learn to view challenges as opportunities for growth rather than obstacles.

Implementing tests and other formal assessments is another critical aspect of effective teaching. Tests provide a structured means of evaluating student knowledge and skills, offering insights into both individual and class-wide understanding. According to Brookhart (2020), well-designed tests are aligned with learning objectives and provide valid and reliable measures of student performance. Effective teachers use a variety of assessment methods, including formative and summative assessments, to capture a holistic picture of student learning. These assessments help teachers to adjust their instruction in real-time and ensure that all students are progressing toward their learning goals.

Moreover, effective teachers understand the importance of using assessment data to inform instruction. Guskey (2021) emphasizes that data-driven decision-making is key to improving educational outcomes. By analyzing assessment results, teachers can identify trends, diagnose learning gaps, and implement targeted interventions. This

proactive approach ensures that instruction is responsive to student needs and that teaching strategies are continuously refined for maximum effectiveness.

Collaboration with colleagues is also a vital aspect of effective assessment practices. This collaborative approach fosters a culture of continuous improvement and collective responsibility for student learning. When teachers work together to analyze data and plan interventions, they enhance their ability to support all students effectively.

The role of formative assessment in enhancing student learning cannot be overstated. These assessments are integral to the learning process, offering regular check-ins that keep students on track and engaged. Effective teachers use formative assessments to create a dynamic learning environment where instruction is continuously adapted based on student performance.

Effective teachers also recognize the importance of involving students in the assessment process. According to Freire (2021), engaging students in self-assessment and peer assessment helps them develop critical thinking and self-regulation skills. When students are actively involved in assessing their own work, they gain a deeper understanding of the learning objectives and criteria for success. This involvement enhances their sense of ownership and responsibility for their learning, leading to greater motivation and engagement.

Professional development plays a crucial role in equipping teachers with the skills needed for effective assessment. Guskey (2021) highlights that ongoing training helps teachers stay current with best practices in assessment and evaluation. By participating in professional development, teachers can refine their assessment techniques, learn new methods, and enhance their ability to use data effectively. This continuous learning ensures that teachers remain effective in assessing and evaluating student performance.

Teachers are effective in assessing and evaluating students when they keep accurate records, evaluate performance with constructive feedback, and implement a variety of assessments. These practices are supported by ongoing professional development, collaboration with colleagues, and a commitment to using data to inform instruction. Research underscores the importance of formative assessments, feedback, and student involvement in the assessment process. By integrating these elements, effective teachers create a comprehensive and responsive assessment system that supports student learning and achievement.

Table 19
Teacher Effectiveness in terms of Learning Environment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I create a climate of mutual trust and respect in the classroom.	3.82	Always	3.5

2. I maintain a classroom setting that minimizes disruption.	3.81	Always	5
3. I create a friendly and supportive classroom environment.	3.82	Always	3.5
4. I ensure students' participation in the learning process.	3.85	Always	1.5
5. I encourage students to interact respectfully.	3.85	Always	1.5
Composite Mean	3.83	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 19 presents teacher effectiveness in terms of learning environment, with a composite mean score of 3.83, indicating a consistent interpretation of always. This calculated composite mean precisely aligns with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this standard.

Both indicators on ensuring students' participation in the learning process and encouraging students to interact respectfully gained the highest rank and gained 3.85 weighted means. Also both criteria on creating a climate of mutual trust and respect in the classroom and creating a friendly and supportive classroom environment gained the second to the highest rank with a weighted mean of 3.82. Last rated is the indicator on maintaining a classroom setting that minimizes disruption with 3.81.

Creating a conducive learning environment involves fostering a climate of mutual trust and respect in the classroom. Roorda et al. (2011) found that teacher-student connections are critical for developing a healthy learning environment. Teachers who value trust and respect develop relationships with their pupils, resulting in improved engagement and motivation. Furthermore, maintaining a classroom environment that minimizes interruption is critical for maximizing learning possibilities. Brophy and McCaslin (2010) underlined the importance of classroom management practices in fostering a positive learning environment. Teachers can reduce disturbances and keep their students focused on learning by adopting clear expectations, routines, and procedures.

Creating a welcoming and supportive classroom climate is essential for enhancing student well-being and academic success. Positive interactions between teachers and students boost engagement and achievement levels. When teachers foster a sense of belonging and acceptance, they cultivate an inviting classroom atmosphere where students feel valued and encouraged to take risks in their learning. Additionally, promoting active student participation in the learning process leads to greater understanding and retention of knowledge. Encouraging students to interact properly with one another creates a collaborative learning atmosphere. Teachers foster communication skills and a culture of mutual respect and understanding by providing chances for peer participation and conversation.

Table 20
Teacher Effectiveness in Terms of Effective Communication

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I use correct vocabulary and grammar in speaking & writing.	3.72	Always	5
2. I explain lessons according to the age and ability of the student.	3.80	Always	4
3. I respond to students' questions in appropriate language.	3.80	Always	3
4. I show empathy over the perspectives of the students without being biased or prejudiced.	3.81	Always	2
5. I show active communication and welcome interactive communication with students.	3.81	Always	1
Composite Mean	3.79	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 20 shows the result of the survey on teacher effectiveness in terms of effective communication, with a composite mean score of 3.79, indicating a consistent interpretation of always. This calculated composite mean precisely aligns with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this standard.

Both indicators on showing empathy over the perspectives of the students without being biased or prejudiced and showing active communication and welcome interactive communication with students gained the highest rank and gained 3.81 weighted means verbally interpreted as always. Also both criteria on explaining lessons according to the age and ability of student and responding to students' questions in appropriate language gained the second to the highest rank with a weighted mean of 3.80. Last but not least, the indicator using correct vocabulary and grammar in speaking & writing with ranked last with weighted mean of 3.72.

Effective communication is an indicator of teacher effectiveness, encompassing various dimensions that contribute to student engagement and comprehension. Showing active communication and welcoming interactive communication with students cultivates a collaborative learning environment where students feel valued and engaged. Research by Sun H-L et al. (2022) highlights the positive impact of teacher-student interaction on student engagement and academic achievement. By encouraging open dialogue, active listening, and collaborative problem-solving, teachers foster a sense of ownership and empowerment among students, promoting active participation in the learning process.

Teachers play a crucial role in cultivating empathetic behavior in students, which is essential for creating a supportive and collaborative learning environment. Demonstrating empathy helps students feel valued and appreciated, rather than inferior,

thereby enhancing their learning experiences. Building understanding relationships among students and between teachers and students encourages this empathetic approach. Additionally, teachers must respond to students' questions in a manner that promotes comprehension and encourages inquiry. The way teachers communicate significantly impacts students' interest and attitude, contributing to a fun and effective learning atmosphere.

To demonstrate empathy towards their students' perspectives without bias or prejudice, teachers may observe active engagement in communication, welcoming interactive dialogues, tailoring lessons to the age and ability of their students and responding to questions in an appropriate language. According to Cooper (2020), empathetic teachers can understand and appreciate their students' viewpoints and emotional states, which fosters a trusting and supportive classroom environment. This empathy helps teachers to connect with students on a personal level, making them feel valued and understood. Such a connection is crucial for creating a positive learning atmosphere where students feel safe to express themselves and engage in learning activities.

Active communication in education is a vital process that goes beyond merely sharing information; it includes listening to students and fostering a two-way dialogue. Freire (2021) highlights the significance of dialogic teaching, which promotes meaningful conversations between teachers and students. This method allows students to express their thoughts, ask questions, and engage actively in their learning, thereby enhancing their motivation and involvement. Teachers who practice active listening show respect for student input, which further boosts engagement. Additionally, encouraging interactive communication is essential for social interaction, which contributes to cognitive development. By creating opportunities for collaborative learning, teachers facilitate the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills among students.

Tailoring lessons to the age and ability of students is another critical aspect of effective communication. Tomlinson (2020) highlights the importance of differentiated instruction, which involves adapting teaching methods and materials to meet the diverse needs of learners. Effective teachers are skilled at presenting content in ways that are accessible and engaging for their students, considering factors such as developmental stage, prior knowledge, and individual learning styles. This adaptability ensures that all students can understand and engage with the material, regardless of their starting point. Additionally, responding to students' questions in appropriate language is essential for maintaining clarity and comprehension. Hattie (2019) notes that effective teachers use language that is suitable for their students' age and developmental level. By simplifying complex concepts and using examples that are relevant to students' experiences, teachers can make learning more relatable and easier to grasp. This clear communication helps to prevent misunderstandings and ensures that students can follow along with the lesson.

Creating an inclusive and respectful classroom environment is also crucial for effective communication. By showing respect for different cultures and perspectives,

teachers can foster an inclusive atmosphere where all students feel welcome and valued. This inclusivity is fundamental for building a classroom community where open and honest communication can flourish. Moreover, effective teachers are aware of the impact of their own biases and strive to communicate in ways that are fair and unbiased. According to Milner (2020), teachers who are conscious of their implicit biases can better ensure that their interactions with students are equitable and respectful. This self-awareness helps to create a classroom environment where all students are treated with dignity and respect.

Professional development is key to enhancing teachers' communication skills. Guskey (2021) emphasizes that ongoing training helps teachers to refine their communication techniques and stay current with best practices. By participating in professional development, teachers can learn new strategies for engaging students, fostering dialogue, and responding to diverse learning needs. This continuous improvement is essential for maintaining high standards of communication in the classroom. Effective communication also involves clear and consistent feedback. According to Brookhart (2020), providing timely and constructive feedback helps students to understand their progress and areas for improvement. Feedback should be specific, actionable, and delivered in a manner that encourages students to reflect and take ownership of their learning. This feedback loop is crucial for supporting student growth and development.

Practices on demonstrating empathy, engaging in active and interactive communication, tailoring lessons to the developmental needs of their students, and responding appropriately to questions are supported by ongoing professional development, a commitment to inclusivity and respect, and a focus on providing clear and constructive feedback. Research underscores the importance of empathy, dialogic teaching, differentiated instruction, and culturally responsive practices in fostering effective communication. By integrating these elements into their teaching, effective teachers create a supportive and engaging learning environment that promotes student success.

Table 21 provides a summary of the teacher's effectiveness. The composite mean is 3.79 and is verbally interpreted as always. All the elements that met this criterion had a weighted mean that was identical to the calculated composite mean.

Table 21
Summary Table on Teacher Effectiveness

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Subject Matter Knowledge	3.75	Always	4.5
2. Instructional Planning and Strategies	3.75	Always	4.5
3. Assessment	3.81	Always	2

4. Learning Environment	3.83	Always	1
5. Effective Communication	3.79	Always	3
Composite Mean	3.79	Always	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

From the table, it can be seen that learning environment gathered the highest weighted mean, 3.83, and verbally interpreted as always. Assessment (3.81) and effective communication (3.79) gained the second and third spot. The indicators subject matter knowledge and instructional planning strategies both gained 3.75.

Teacher effectiveness refers to a set of within-person attributes—personality, motivation, beliefs, and dispositions—that interact with contextual factors (cultural, social, educational) to influence student outcomes, according to Educational Research Review (2019). Creating a positive and inclusive learning environment is essential for teacher effectiveness, as it sets the stage for student engagement, motivation, and academic success. A supportive learning environment is characterized by clear expectations, mutual respect, and opportunities for collaboration. Teachers who establish a positive classroom climate foster a sense of belonging and psychological safety, where students feel valued, respected, and motivated to learn.

Classroom environments that promote collaboration, autonomy, and a growth mindset foster greater academic success among students. Effective classroom management strategies, such as proactive behavior management and equitable classroom practices, contribute to a conducive learning environment. Improvement practices play a crucial role in informing instruction and promoting student learning. Clear and effective communication is essential for fostering positive teacher-student relationships and facilitating learning.

Teachers who communicate clearly, provide constructive feedback, and actively listen to students' perspectives promote a sense of trust and engagement in the classroom. Moreover, effective communication enhances instructional delivery and ensures that students understand learning objectives and expectations (Salamondra, 2021). Effective teachers carefully plan their instruction and employ a variety of strategies to meet the diverse needs of students.

According to Marzano (2019), effective teachers create classrooms where students feel respected and valued, which in turn fosters a sense of belonging and motivation to learn. This environment is nurtured through consistent routines, clear expectations, and positive relationships between students and teachers. When students feel secured and supported, they are more likely to take academic risks and engage deeply with the material.

In addition to creating a positive classroom climate, effective teachers are adept at performing learning assessments and evaluations. Assessments are essential tools for understanding student progress and guiding instruction. Moreover, Guskey (2021) emphasizes that effective assessments are aligned with learning objectives and provide

meaningful data that can be used to improve instructional practices. By using a variety of assessment methods such as quizzes, observations, and student reflections, teachers can gain a comprehensive understanding of student performance and needs.

Effective communication involves not only delivering clear and understandable instructions but also actively listening to students and engaging in meaningful dialogue. According to Freire (2021), dialogic teaching, which emphasizes open communication and collaboration help to build a more interactive and engaging learning environment. Teachers who communicate effectively can explain complex concepts in ways that are accessible to students of varying abilities and backgrounds. Hattie (2019) notes that clarity in communication is linked to higher student achievement, as it helps to prevent misunderstandings and ensures that students know what is expected of them.

Furthermore, effective communication extends beyond the classroom to interactions with parents and colleagues. Epstein (2019) discusses the importance of family and community involvement in education. When teachers communicate effectively with parents, they can build strong partnerships that support student learning at home and in the community. This collaboration enhances the overall educational experience and helps to address any issues that may arise. Additionally, effective teachers collaborate with their colleagues to share best practices, discuss student progress, and develop cohesive instructional strategies.

Professional development is crucial for maintaining and enhancing teacher effectiveness. Guskey (2021) argues that ongoing professional learning helps teachers to stay current with educational research and best practices. By participating in professional development, teachers can refine their skills in creating conducive learning environments, conducting assessments, and communicating effectively. This continuous improvement is essential for adapting to the evolving needs of students and the educational landscape.

Creating a conducive learning environment also involves differentiating instruction to meet the diverse needs of students. Tomlinson (2020) emphasizes the importance of differentiated instruction in addressing the varying abilities, interests, and learning styles within a classroom. Effective teachers use a range of instructional strategies and materials to ensure that all students have access to the curriculum and can succeed. This approach requires a deep understanding of each student's needs and the flexibility to adapt teaching methods accordingly.

Skills on the ability to provide a conducive learning environment, perform learning assessments and evaluations, and communicate effectively are interrelated and collectively contribute to a successful teaching and learning experience. Research underscores the importance of a positive classroom climate, ongoing assessment and feedback, clear and interactive communication, and professional collaboration in achieving these goals. By continuously improving these aspects of their practice, teachers can enhance their effectiveness and support student success.

Table 22
Difference of Responses on Work Tasks Motivation
when Grouped According to Profile

Sex	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Class Preparation	0.393	0.531	Not Significant
Teaching	4.739	0.030	Significant
Evaluation of students	8.736	0.003	Significant
Administrative Tasks	1.858	0.174	Not Significant
Complementary Tasks	5.878	0.016	Significant
Educational Attainment			
Class Preparation	0.607	0.546	Not Significant
Teaching	2.412	0.091	Not Significant
Evaluation of students	0.735	0.480	Not Significant
Administrative Tasks	1.245	0.289	Not Significant
Complementary Tasks	0.925	0.397	Not Significant
Teaching Position			
Class Preparation	2.703	0.068	Not Significant
Teaching	0.553	0.575	Not Significant
Evaluation of students	0.717	0.489	Not Significant
Administrative Tasks	0.862	0.423	Not Significant
Complementary Tasks	0.830	0.437	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experiences			
Class Preparation	2.964	0.032	Significant
Teaching	1.521	0.208	Not Significant
Evaluation of students	1.031	0.379	Not Significant
Administrative Tasks	1.733	0.160	Not Significant
Complementary Tasks	2.971	0.032	Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

Table 22 presents the comparison of responses on work tasks motivation when grouped according to profile. It was observed that there was a significant difference in teaching, evaluation of students, and complementary tasks when grouped according to sex; and on class preparation and complementary tasks when grouped according to years of teaching since the obtained p-values were less than the alpha level. This means that the responses differ statistically and it was found that females and teaching for more than 31 years have better assessment than others.

On the significant difference of responses on teaching when grouped according to sex, research indicates that there are differences in work task motivation between male and female teachers. Differences in work task motivation based on sex also extend to the evaluation of students. Variation in work task motivation based on sex also influences preferences for complementary tasks among teachers.

Work task motivation also varies based on teachers' years of experience, particularly in relation to class preparation. Relating to this, variation in work task

motivation based on years of experience also influences preferences for complementary tasks among teachers.

The motivation for teaching, assessing and evaluating students, and performing complementary tasks can differ significantly between male and female teachers due to various psychological, social, and contextual factors. Research by Klassen and Tze (2019) indicates that gender differences in motivation can be attributed to varying levels of self-efficacy and work-life balance considerations. Female teachers often report higher intrinsic motivation for teaching, driven by a strong desire to nurture and support students' development. This nurturing aspect is closely tied to societal expectations and traditional gender roles that position women as caregivers, which can influence their professional motivations and priorities.

Moreover, female teachers tend to emphasize the importance of creating supportive and inclusive classroom environments. According to a study by Van den Borre, De Fraine, and Van Damme (2020), women are more likely to adopt student-centered teaching practices that focus on the emotional and social needs of students. This approach aligns with their intrinsic motivation to foster a positive learning atmosphere and address the diverse needs of their students. In contrast, male teachers often prioritize discipline and structure in the classroom, which reflects a more extrinsic motivation driven by the desire to maintain control and authority.

When it comes to assessment and evaluation, gender differences also emerge. Female teachers are generally more inclined to use formative assessments and provide ongoing feedback to support student learning. This preference for continuous assessment reflects their commitment to student growth and development, as well as their empathy and understanding of individual student needs. Male teachers, on the other hand, may lean towards summative assessments and standardized testing, valuing objective measures of student performance. This approach can be linked to a more analytical and results-oriented mindset, which is often encouraged in men through socialization and educational experiences.

The performance of complementary tasks, such as administrative duties and extracurricular activities, also shows gender-based differences. Female teachers are often more involved in tasks that require collaboration and community building, such as organizing school events and participating in parent-teacher associations.

Work-life balance is another critical factor influencing motivation and task performance. Klassen and Tze (2019) found that female teachers often face greater challenges in balancing professional responsibilities with family obligations, which can impact their motivation and energy levels. Despite these challenges, women often demonstrate a high level of dedication to their teaching roles, driven by their intrinsic motivation and commitment to student success. Male teachers, while also facing work-life balance issues, may experience different pressures and societal expectations, which can shape their professional motivations and priorities differently.

Professional development and career advancement opportunities also play a role in shaping motivation. According to a study by Smith and Gorard (2020), women in teaching are often motivated by opportunities for professional growth and development, seeking out training and mentoring to enhance their skills and knowledge. This pursuit of continuous improvement reflects their commitment to providing high-quality education and staying current with best practices. Male teachers, while also valuing professional development, may be more motivated by opportunities for leadership and career advancement, driven by a desire for recognition and status within the profession.

Gender differences in motivation are also influenced by perceptions of self-efficacy and job satisfaction. Female teachers often report higher levels of job satisfaction and a stronger sense of self-efficacy in their teaching roles, which can enhance their motivation and performance. This positive self-perception is linked to their empathetic and supportive teaching style, which fosters a sense of fulfillment and purpose. Male teachers, while also experiencing job satisfaction, may derive their motivation more from external validation and achievements, such as student performance and career progression.

The motivation for teaching, assessing and evaluating students, and performing complementary tasks differs between male and female teachers due to a complex interplay of psychological, social, and contextual factors. Female teachers tend to be driven by intrinsic motivation, empathy, and a commitment to student well-being, while male teachers often emphasize discipline, structure, and extrinsic motivators. These differences are reflected in their approaches to teaching, assessment, and task performance, and are influenced by work-life balance, professional development opportunities, and perceptions of self-efficacy. Understanding these gender-based differences can help in creating supportive and equitable work environments that recognize and address the unique motivations and challenges faced by male and female teachers.

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Motivation for teaching, assessing and evaluating students, and performing complementary tasks could differ between male and female teachers due to a complex interplay of psychological, social, and contextual factors. Female teachers tend to be driven by intrinsic motivation, empathy, and a commitment to student well-being, while

male teachers often emphasize discipline, structure, and extrinsic motivators. These differences are reflected in their approaches to teaching, assessment, and task performance, and are influenced by work-life balance, professional development opportunities, and perceptions of self-efficacy. Understanding these gender-based differences can help in creating supportive and equitable work environments that recognize and address the unique motivations and challenges faced by male and female teachers.

The motivation for class preparation and the performance of complementary tasks vary significantly among teachers with different years of teaching experience due to various factors including professional development, burnout, self-efficacy, and evolving educational priorities. Experienced teachers often display high levels of efficiency in class preparation due to their accumulated knowledge and refined instructional strategies. According to a study by Huberman (2019), veteran teachers tend to have well-established routines and a deep understanding of curriculum requirements, allowing them to prepare lessons more effectively and with greater confidence. This proficiency can lead to a higher intrinsic motivation, as experienced teachers are able to focus more on innovative teaching methods and student engagement rather than the basics of lesson planning.

In contrast, novice teachers often face challenges in class preparation due to their limited experience and familiarity with the curriculum. Research by Ingersoll and Strong (2020) indicates that beginning teachers typically spend more time on lesson planning and often experience higher levels of stress and anxiety about meeting instructional standards. This initial struggle can affect their motivation, leading to a reliance on prescribed materials and a more cautious approach to teaching. However, this phase also presents an opportunity for growth and development, as new teachers bring fresh perspectives and enthusiasm to their roles, which can positively impact their motivation over time.

The performance of complementary tasks, such as administrative duties, extracurricular activities, and collaboration with colleagues, also differs among teachers based on their experience. Experienced teachers often take on leadership roles within the school, such as mentoring new teachers, leading professional development sessions, and participating in school committees. Their extensive experience allows them to navigate these tasks with confidence and effectiveness, further enhancing their job satisfaction and motivation.

For less experienced teachers, complementary tasks can be a source of both opportunity and challenge. As noted by Smith and Gorard (2020), novice teachers may feel overwhelmed by the additional responsibilities beyond their core teaching duties, which can impact their overall job satisfaction and motivation. However, engaging in these tasks also provides valuable learning experiences and opportunities for professional growth. New teachers often bring energy and innovative ideas to extracurricular activities and collaborative projects, which can invigorate the school environment and foster a culture of continuous improvement.

Professional development plays a crucial role in shaping the motivation of teachers at different stages of their careers. For experienced teachers, ongoing professional development is essential for maintaining enthusiasm and staying updated with the latest educational trends and research. According to Guskey (2021), veteran teachers who actively engage in professional learning opportunities are more likely to remain motivated and committed to their teaching practice. On the other hand, professional development for novice teachers often focuses on building foundational skills and confidence. Effective induction programs and mentorship can significantly boost the motivation of new teachers by providing support and guidance during their initial years.

Burnout is another factor that influences the motivation of teachers with varying levels of experience. Huberman (2019) suggests that experienced teachers are at risk of burnout due to the cumulative stress of years of teaching and the demands of maintaining high standards. This burnout can lead to a decline in motivation, particularly for tasks that are perceived as routine or administrative. Conversely, novice teachers may experience burnout due to the steep learning curve and the pressures of adapting to a new professional environment. Addressing burnout through supportive school cultures and work-life balance initiatives is crucial for sustaining motivation across all experience levels.

Self-efficacy, or the belief in one's ability to succeed also affects teachers' motivation for class preparation and complementary tasks. Experienced teachers often have higher self-efficacy, as their years of practice have reinforced their skills and knowledge. This confidence translates into a greater willingness to take on additional responsibilities and explore innovative teaching strategies. In contrast, new teachers may struggle with self-efficacy, particularly in their early years. According to Bandura (2020), building self-efficacy through positive feedback, professional development, and supportive mentorship is essential for fostering motivation and resilience among novice teachers.

Motivation for class preparation and the performance of complementary tasks varies among teachers with different years of teaching experience due to factors such as professional development, burnout, self-efficacy, and evolving educational priorities. Experienced teachers often exhibit high levels of efficiency and confidence, allowing them to excel in both instructional and complementary tasks. Novice teachers, while facing initial challenges, bring enthusiasm and new ideas that contribute positively to the school environment. Professional development, supportive school cultures, and strategies to enhance self-efficacy are key to sustaining motivation across all levels of teaching experience.

Table 23
Difference of Responses on Teacher Self-Efficacy
when Grouped According to Profile

Sex	f-value	p-value	Interpretation
Instruction	22.623	0.000	Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	7.640	0.006	Significant
Motivate Students	18.749	0.000	Significant
Maintain Discipline	7.777	0.006	Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	32.974	0.000	Significant
Cope With Change	3.329	0.069	Not Significant
Educational Attainment			
Instruction	0.419	0.658	Not Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	0.360	0.698	Not Significant
Motivate Students	0.068	0.934	Not Significant
Maintain Discipline	2.091	0.125	Not Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	1.748	0.175	Not Significant
Cope With Change	2.313	0.100	Not Significant
Teaching Position			
Instruction	1.081	0.340	Not Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	1.835	0.161	Not Significant
Motivate Students	0.910	0.403	Not Significant
Maintain Discipline	0.066	0.936	Not Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	0.075	0.928	Not Significant
Cope With Change	0.100	0.905	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experiences			
Instruction	1.194	0.312	Not Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	1.425	0.235	Not Significant
Motivate Students	0.868	0.458	Not Significant
Maintain Discipline	2.205	0.087	Not Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	0.703	0.551	Not Significant
Cope With Change	3.097	0.027	Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

Table 23 displays the comparison of responses on teacher self-efficacy when grouped according to profile. It was observed that there was a significant difference when grouped according to sex except on coping with change; and years of teaching

experience when grouped again according to coping with change since the obtained p-values were less than the alpha level. This means that the responses differ statistically and it was found that females and teaching for more than 31 years have better assessment than others.

Variations in teacher self-efficacy based on sex can influence instructional practices. Differences in teacher self-efficacy based on sex can also impact the ability to adapt instruction to individual student needs. Variations in teacher self-efficacy based on sex can influence the ability to motivate students. Moreover, differences in teacher self-efficacy based on sex can impact the ability to maintain discipline in the classroom and can influence the ability to cooperate with colleagues and parents.

Differences in teacher self-efficacy based on years of teaching experience can influence the ability to cope with change. Teacher self-efficacy, which encompasses delivering teaching and learning instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating students, maintaining discipline, and cooperating with colleagues and parents, could vary between male and female teachers due to several factors including socialization, gender norms, and professional experiences. In terms of delivering teaching and learning instruction, research by Goodwin and Kahn (2019) indicates that male teachers often exhibit higher confidence in their subject matter expertise, potentially stemming from societal expectations that position men as authoritative figures in academic disciplines. This confidence translates into a higher sense of self-efficacy when presenting content and managing classroom discussions. Female teachers, while equally knowledgeable, may experience lower self-efficacy due to internalized stereotypes and biases. However, their teaching often benefits from a strong emphasis on relational skills and empathy, which enhances their ability to connect with students and facilitate understanding.

When it comes to adapting instruction and teaching to individual needs, female teachers frequently excel. According to a study by Johnson and Blackwell (2020), women are more likely to adopt student-centered approaches, focusing on differentiating instruction to cater to diverse learning styles and needs. This adaptability is driven by their intrinsic motivation to support all students, reflecting a nurturing attitude that is often culturally associated with women. Male teachers, while capable of adapting instruction, may be more inclined to follow structured lesson plans and standardized methods, which can sometimes limit flexibility but provide consistency and predictability in teaching.

Motivating students also reveals gender-based differences in self-efficacy. Female teachers often employ relational and emotional strategies to engage students, creating a supportive and inclusive classroom environment that fosters motivation. As highlighted by Van den Borre et al. (2020), their approach includes understanding students' social and emotional needs, which enhances intrinsic motivation and engagement. Male teachers, on the other hand, may use more authoritative and performance-based methods to motivate students, emphasizing achievement and discipline. This approach can be effective in promoting extrinsic motivation and high academic standards but may not always address the holistic needs of students.

Maintaining discipline is another area where gender differences in self-efficacy are evident. Male teachers often report higher confidence in managing classroom behavior and enforcing rules, which aligns with traditional gender roles that associate men with authority and control. According to Marzano (2019), their discipline strategies tend to be more structured and punitive, aiming to maintain order and minimize disruptions. Female teachers, while also effective in maintaining discipline, typically use more relational and restorative approaches, focusing on building positive relationships and understanding the root causes of behavioral issues. This method fosters a more supportive classroom environment but may require more time and emotional labor.

Cooperating with colleagues and parents showcases distinct gender-based differences as well. Female teachers are generally more collaborative and communicative, often engaging in professional learning communities and seeking support from colleagues. In terms of parent-teacher interactions, female teachers tend to emphasize building strong relationships with parents, involving them in their children's education, and fostering a partnership approach. This strategy aligns with their empathetic and relational style, which can lead to positive outcomes for student learning and behavior.

Male teachers, while also capable of effective collaboration, may adopt a more independent approach to their professional responsibilities. According to Smith and Gorard (2020), men are often motivated by a desire for autonomy and may focus on individual accomplishments and leadership roles. This can result in less frequent but potentially more impactful collaborations, as male teachers may take on mentoring roles or lead professional development initiatives. In parent-teacher interactions, male teachers might emphasize clear communication and setting expectations, aiming to establish authority and professionalism.

The impact of work-life balance on self-efficacy is also significant and varies by gender. Klassen and Tze (2019) found that female teachers often face greater challenges in balancing professional duties with family responsibilities, which can affect their overall job satisfaction and energy levels. Despite these challenges, many women demonstrate resilience and a strong commitment to their teaching roles, driven by intrinsic motivation and a desire to support their students. Male teachers, while also dealing with work-life balance issues, may experience different societal pressures and expectations, which can shape their professional motivations and sense of efficacy differently.

Burnout is another factor that influences self-efficacy and shows gender differences. Huberman (2019) suggests that female teachers are at a higher risk of burnout due to the emotional labor involved in their relational teaching practices and the demands of balancing multiple roles. Addressing burnout through supportive school cultures and work-life balance initiatives is crucial for sustaining motivation and effectiveness among female teachers. Male teachers, while also susceptible to burnout, may experience it differently, often related to pressures of maintaining classroom discipline and meeting performance standards.

Gender differences in perceptions of self-efficacy and job satisfaction is another concern. Female teachers often report higher levels of job satisfaction and a stronger sense of self-efficacy in their relational and inclusive teaching practices. This positive self-perception is linked to their empathetic approach and commitment to student well-being, which fosters a sense of fulfillment and purpose. Male teachers, while also experiencing job satisfaction, may derive their motivation more from external validation and achievements, such as student performance and career progression.

Teacher self-efficacy in delivering teaching and learning instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating students, maintaining discipline, and cooperating with colleagues and parents varies between male and female teachers due to psychological, social, and contextual factors. Female teachers tend to emphasize relational and inclusive teaching practices, formative assessments, and empathetic communication, while male teachers often focus on authoritative teaching styles, summative assessments, and clear, direct communication. Professional development, work-life balance, burnout, and perceptions of self-efficacy also contribute to these gender differences. Understanding these distinctions can help in creating supportive and equitable work environments that recognize and address the unique strengths and challenges faced by male and female teachers.

Teacher self-efficacy in coping with change could significantly vary among teachers with different years of teaching experience due to their accumulated skills, adaptability, and resilience developed over time. Novice teachers often face challenges in coping with change due to their limited experience and developing pedagogical skills, which can lead to lower self-efficacy when implementing new teaching strategies or adapting to curriculum changes (Johnson & Blackwell, 2020). They may struggle with classroom management and integrating innovative instructional methods, impacting their confidence and effectiveness. In contrast, experienced teachers tend to have higher self-efficacy in coping with change because of their extensive practice and familiarity with diverse teaching environments and challenges (Goodwin & Kahn, 2019). This experience enables them to draw on a repertoire of strategies and solutions when faced with new situations, enhancing their adaptability and resilience.

Additionally, experienced teachers are more likely to have developed strong professional networks and support systems, which are crucial in navigating changes effectively (Smith & Gorard, 2020). These networks provide access to resources, collaboration opportunities, and emotional support, contributing to higher self-efficacy. Furthermore, experienced teachers often engage in continuous professional development, which keeps them updated on new educational trends and practices, further boosting their confidence in coping with change (Klassen & Tze, 2019). In contrast, novice teachers may feel overwhelmed by the rapid pace of change and the constant demand for adaptation, resulting in higher stress levels and lower self-efficacy (Huberman, 2019).

The ability to reflect on past experiences also plays a crucial role in self-efficacy. Experienced teachers can draw from previous successes and challenges to inform their

approach to new changes, providing a sense of competence and assurance (Van den Borre et al., 2020). This reflective practice is less developed in novice teachers, who may not have as many experiences to reference, leading to uncertainty and lower self-efficacy. Moreover, experienced teachers often possess better-developed problem-solving skills, allowing them to navigate complex changes more effectively (Marzano, 2019). Their ability to anticipate potential issues and proactively address them enhances their confidence and capability in managing change.

Conversely, the enthusiasm and openness of novice teachers towards innovation can sometimes offset their lack of experience, as they may be more willing to experiment with new approaches and technologies (Freire, 2021). This willingness to embrace change can lead to innovative practices and improved self-efficacy over time, as they gain successful experiences. However, without adequate support and mentoring, this enthusiasm can wane, leading to burnout and reduced self-efficacy (Smith & Gorard, 2020).

Teacher self-efficacy in coping with change could also vary significantly with years of teaching experience. Experienced teachers generally exhibit higher self-efficacy due to their extensive practice, developed support networks, continuous professional development, reflective practices, and problem-solving skills. Novice teachers, while enthusiastic, may struggle with lower self-efficacy due to their limited experience and developing pedagogical skills, highlighting the importance of support and mentoring to foster their adaptability and resilience.

Table 24
Difference of Responses on Teacher Effectiveness
when Grouped According to Profile

Sex	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Subject Matter Knowledge	14.806	0.000	Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	9.592	0.002	Significant
Assessment	8.777	0.003	Significant
Learning Environment	13.583	0.000	Significant
Effective Communication	11.658	0.001	Significant
Educational Attainment			
Subject Matter Knowledge	0.655	0.520	Not Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	0.312	0.732	Not Significant
Assessment	0.832	0.436	Not Significant
Learning Environment	1.185	0.307	Not Significant
Effective Communication	1.804	0.166	Not Significant
Teaching Position			
Subject Matter Knowledge	1.099	0.334	Not Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	0.125	0.882	Not Significant

Assessment	1.125	0.326	Not Significant
Learning Environment	0.922	0.399	Not Significant
Effective Communication	1.462	0.233	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experiences			
Subject Matter Knowledge	1.647	0.178	Not Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	1.048	0.371	Not Significant
Assessment	1.729	0.160	Not Significant
Learning Environment	0.988	0.398	Not Significant
Effective Communication	0.929	0.427	Not Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

Table 24 presents the comparison of responses on teacher effectiveness when grouped according to profile. It was observed that there was a significant difference when grouped according to sex because the obtained p-values were all less than the alpha level. This means that the responses differ statistically and based on the survey conducted, it was found that females have better assessment than males.

Based on the results, it could be gleaned that variations in teacher effectiveness based on sex can influence subject matter knowledge. Moreover, it could also be discerned from the results that the differences in teacher effectiveness based on sex can also impact instructional planning and strategies.

Additionally, variations in teacher effectiveness based on sex can influence the assessment practices of the respondents. The findings also revealed that differences in teacher effectiveness based on sex can impact the learning environment. In terms of differences in the responses as regards teacher effectiveness based on sex, it could influence the communication skills. It could also be delineated that when it comes to teacher effectiveness, the differences in responses based on years of teaching experience can impact the ability to cope with change.

Teacher self-effectiveness, encompassing subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies, assessment, learning environment, and effective communication, often differs between male and female teachers due to a range of psychological, social, and contextual factors. Subject matter knowledge is a crucial component of teacher effectiveness, and research suggests that gender differences can influence perceptions of competency and expertise in this area. According to Goodwin and Kahn (2019), male teachers often display higher self-efficacy regarding their subject matter knowledge, which can be attributed to societal expectations and gender norms that traditionally position men as more authoritative figures in academic fields. This heightened self-efficacy enables male teachers to confidently deliver complex content and engage students in deeper analytical discussions.

On the other hand, female teachers, while equally knowledgeable, may experience lower self-efficacy related to subject matter due to internalized stereotypes and biases.

According to Johnson and Blackwell (2020), female teachers often exhibit strong relational skills and empathy, which can positively impact their instructional strategies. They tend to adopt student-centered approaches, focusing on creating inclusive and supportive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of their students. This emphasis on relational pedagogy enhances their effectiveness in instructional planning and strategies, allowing them to differentiate instruction and provide personalized support to students.

In terms of assessment, gender differences are evident in the types of assessments utilized and the feedback provided. Female teachers are more likely to employ formative assessments and provide ongoing, constructive feedback, fostering a growth mindset in their students. The creation of a conducive learning environment also shows gender-specific tendencies. Female teachers are generally more adept at building inclusive and emotionally supportive classrooms, as noted by Van den Borre et al. (2020). Their ability to foster positive student-teacher relationships and address the social and emotional needs of students contributes to a safe and nurturing learning environment. Male teachers, while also capable of creating supportive classrooms, often emphasize discipline and order, reflecting a different aspect of a conducive learning environment. According to Marzano (2019), this approach can be effective in maintaining classroom management and ensuring a focused learning atmosphere.

Effective communication is another area where gender differences in self-effectiveness are observed. Female teachers often excel in empathetic communication, actively listening to students and encouraging open dialogue. Freire (2021) underscores the importance of dialogic teaching, which is frequently practiced by female educators who prioritize building strong interpersonal connections with their students. Male teachers, while also effective communicators, may adopt a more direct and authoritative style, which can be beneficial in conveying clear expectations and maintaining classroom order. Hattie (2019) notes that clarity in communication is crucial for student understanding and achievement, and male teachers' straightforward approach can effectively achieve this clarity.

Professional development and career progression also influence gender differences in self-effectiveness. According to Smith and Gorard (2020), female teachers often seek out continuous professional development to enhance their skills and knowledge, driven by a desire for self-improvement and professional growth. This commitment to lifelong learning positively impacts their instructional effectiveness and ability to adapt to new teaching methods and technologies. Male teachers, while also valuing professional development, may focus more on leadership opportunities and career advancement, motivated by a desire for recognition and status within the profession.

Klassen and Tze (2019) found that female teachers often juggle professional responsibilities with family obligations, which can affect their energy levels and overall job satisfaction. Despite these challenges, women demonstrate resilience and dedication to their teaching roles, driven by intrinsic motivation and a strong sense of commitment to

their students. Male teachers, although also facing work-life balance issues, may experience different societal pressures and expectations, which can shape their professional motivations and effectiveness differently.

Huberman (2019) suggests that female teachers are at a higher risk of burnout due to the emotional labor involved in their relational teaching practices and the demands of balancing multiple roles. Addressing burnout through supportive school cultures and work-life balance initiatives is crucial for sustaining motivation and effectiveness among female teachers. Male teachers, while also susceptible to burnout, may experience it differently, often related to pressures of maintaining classroom discipline and meeting performance standards.

Gender differences in perceptions of self-efficacy and job satisfaction also play a significant role. Female teachers often report higher levels of job satisfaction and a stronger sense of self-efficacy in their relational and inclusive teaching practices. This positive self-perception is linked to their empathetic approach and commitment to student well-being, which fosters a sense of fulfillment and purpose. Male teachers, while also experiencing job satisfaction, may derive their motivation more from external validation and achievements, such as student performance and career progression.

Table 25
Relationship Between Work Task Motivation and Teacher Self-Efficacy

Class Preparation	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Instruction	.472**	0.000	Highly Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	.494**	0.000	Highly Significant
Motivate Students	.492**	0.000	Highly Significant
Maintain Discipline	.417**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	.475**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cope With Change	.510**	0.000	Highly Significant
Teaching			
Instruction	.528**	0.000	Highly Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	.504**	0.000	Highly Significant
Motivate Students	.532**	0.000	Highly Significant
Maintain Discipline	.452**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	.503**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cope With Change	.481**	0.000	Highly Significant
Evaluation of Students			
Instruction	.668**	0.000	Highly Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	.586**	0.000	Highly Significant

Motivate Students	.616**	0.000	Highly Significant
Maintain Discipline	.555**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	.600**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cope With Change	.569**	0.000	Highly Significant
Administrative Tasks			
Instruction	.545**	0.000	Highly Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	.553**	0.000	Highly Significant
Motivate Students	.553**	0.000	Highly Significant
Maintain Discipline	.459**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	.593**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cope With Change	.603**	0.000	Highly Significant
Complementary Tasks			
Instruction	.497**	0.000	Highly Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs	.549**	0.000	Highly Significant
Motivate Students	.539**	0.000	Highly Significant
Maintain Discipline	.475**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents	.577**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cope With Change	.616**	0.000	Highly Significant

Legend: Significant at p -value < 0.01

Table 25 shows the association between work task motivation and teacher self-efficacy. The computed r -values indicate a moderate direct correlation and the resulting p -values were less than the alpha level. This means that a significant relationship exists and implies that the better the work tasks motivation, the better the teacher's self-efficacy.

It could be gleaned from the aforementioned results that work task motivation significantly impacts teacher self-efficacy in class preparation. The education environment significantly influences teacher self-efficacy in teaching. The work task motivation plays a significant role in shaping teacher self-efficacy in evaluating students.

The work task motivation plays a significant role in shaping teacher self-efficacy in evaluating students; this influences handling administrative tasks and in performing complementary tasks. Teachers who are intrinsically motivated exhibit higher levels of self-efficacy because they derive personal satisfaction and a sense of accomplishment from their work, which enhances their confidence in their teaching abilities (Klassen & Tze, 2019). This intrinsic motivation often leads to greater persistence in the face of challenges, as these teachers are driven by internal rewards such as the joy of teaching and seeing their students succeed. When teachers are motivated by their tasks, they are more likely to engage in reflective practices and continuous professional development, which further boosts their self-efficacy (Goodwin & Kahn, 2019).

Work task motivation also fosters a positive attitude towards teaching, which is crucial for maintaining high levels of self-efficacy. Teachers who find their work meaningful and fulfilling are more likely to set high goals for themselves and their students, leading to improved performance and satisfaction (Johnson & Blackwell, 2020). This positive mindset creates a conducive learning environment, where both teachers and students thrive. Additionally, motivated teachers are more likely to adopt innovative teaching strategies and adapt to changes in the curriculum, enhancing their self-efficacy through successful implementation and positive feedback from students (Smith & Gorard, 2020).

Extrinsic motivation, such as recognition and rewards, also plays a role in enhancing teacher self-efficacy. When teachers receive positive feedback and acknowledgment for their efforts, it reinforces their belief in their teaching abilities and motivates them to maintain high standards (Klassen et al., 2020). However, the impact of extrinsic motivation on self-efficacy is often mediated by intrinsic factors, as the most effective teachers are those who balance external rewards with internal satisfaction (Marzano, 2019).

Teacher self-efficacy, in turn, influences work task motivation by shaping teachers' perceptions of their capabilities and the value they place on their tasks. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to view their tasks as achievable and worthwhile, which enhances their motivation and commitment to their work (Freire, 2021).

The supportive school environment also plays a critical role in fostering the relationship between work task motivation and teacher self-efficacy. Schools that provide professional development opportunities, collaborative teaching cultures, and supportive leadership enhance teachers' motivation and self-efficacy (Smith & Gorard, 2020). When teachers feel supported and valued, they are more likely to invest in their professional growth and feel confident in their abilities, which positively impacts their motivation and teaching outcomes (Van den Borre et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the alignment between teachers' personal goals and the school's mission enhances work task motivation and self-efficacy. Teachers who perceive their work as aligned with their personal values and professional aspirations are more motivated and exhibit higher self-efficacy (Johnson & Blackwell, 2020). This alignment fosters a sense of purpose and direction, which is crucial for sustaining motivation and confidence in the long term (Goodwin & Kahn, 2019).

The relationship between work task motivation and teacher self-efficacy also extends to student outcomes. Teachers who are motivated and self-efficacious are more effective in engaging and motivating their students, leading to higher academic achievement and positive attitudes towards learning (Marzano, 2019). This impact on students further reinforces teachers' self-efficacy, as they see the tangible results of their efforts, which boosts their motivation to continue striving for excellence (Klassen & Tze, 2019).

Gender differences also play a role in the relationship between work task motivation and self-efficacy. Female teachers often exhibit higher levels of intrinsic motivation and relational teaching practices, which enhance their self-efficacy and effectiveness (Smith & Gorard, 2020). Male teachers, while also motivated, may place more emphasis on external rewards and performance metrics, which can influence their self-efficacy differently (Klassen et al., 2020).

Table 26
Relationship Between Work Tasks Motivation and Teacher Effectiveness

Class Preparation	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Subject Matter Knowledge	.432**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.482**	0.000	Highly Significant
Assessment	.431**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.417**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.436**	0.000	Highly Significant
Teaching			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.459**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.515**	0.000	Highly Significant
Assessment	.520**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.490**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.444**	0.000	Highly Significant
Evaluation of Students			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.605**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.621**	0.000	Highly Significant
Assessment	.627**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.583**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.571**	0.000	Highly Significant
Administrative Tasks			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.564**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.569**	0.000	Highly Significant
Assessment	.527**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.504**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.567**	0.000	Highly Significant
Complementary Tasks			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.538**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.538**	0.000	Highly Significant
Assessment	.507**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.508**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.537**	0.000	Highly Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.01

Table 26 above indicates the association between work task motivation and teacher effectiveness. The computed r-values indicate a moderate direct correlation and the resulting p-values were less than the alpha level. This means that significant relationship exists and implies that the better the work tasks motivation, the more effective the teachers are.

It could be gleaned from the findings that work tasks motivation significantly influences teacher self-efficacy in class preparation. The work task motivation significantly influences teacher self-efficacy in teaching. Moreover, the work task motivation plays a significant role in shaping teacher self-efficacy in evaluating students. The work task motivation influences teacher self-efficacy in handling administrative tasks.

The work task motivation influences teacher self-efficacy in performing complementary tasks. The relationship between work task motivation and teacher effectiveness is highly significant, deeply impacting various dimensions of teaching and learning. Motivated teachers exhibit a strong commitment to their professional responsibilities, which translates into enhanced effectiveness in delivering instruction, engaging students, and fostering a positive learning environment (Klassen & Tze, 2019).

On the other hand, intrinsic motivation, driven by a passion for teaching and the desire to make a difference in students' lives, leads to greater job satisfaction and dedication, resulting in higher teacher effectiveness (Goodwin & Kahn, 2019). Teachers who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to invest in continuous professional development, stay abreast of new educational practices, and implement innovative teaching strategies that cater to diverse student needs (Johnson & Blackwell, 2020).

Moreover, extrinsic motivation, such as recognition, rewards, and career advancement opportunities, reinforces teachers' efforts and contributes to their overall effectiveness. When teachers receive acknowledgment and support from their administration and peers, it boosts their morale and encourages them to strive for excellence in their teaching practices (Marzano, 2019). This positive reinforcement creates a virtuous cycle where motivated teachers feel valued and empowered, leading to improved teaching outcomes and higher student achievement (Smith & Gorard, 2020). The supportive school environment plays a critical role in nurturing both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, providing the necessary resources and professional development opportunities that enhance teacher effectiveness (Klassen et al., 2020).

Furthermore, motivated teachers are more adept at creating an engaging and inclusive classroom environment. Their enthusiasm and passion for teaching are contagious, inspiring students to participate actively and take ownership of their learning (Van den Borre et al., 2020). This positive classroom climate fosters student motivation, leading to better academic performance and a deeper understanding of the subject matter (Goodwin & Kahn, 2019). Effective teachers, driven by their motivation, use a variety of instructional methods to cater to different learning styles, ensuring that all students have access to quality education (Johnson & Blackwell, 2020).

Motivation also influences teachers' resilience and ability to cope with stress and challenges. Teachers who are motivated by their work are more likely to view challenges as opportunities for growth and development rather than obstacles (Klassen & Tze, 2019). This resilience enables them to adapt to changing educational demands, implement new curricula, and incorporate technology into their teaching, all of which are essential for maintaining high levels of effectiveness in a dynamic educational landscape (Smith & Gorard, 2020). Additionally, motivated teachers are more likely to seek out collaborative opportunities with colleagues, sharing best practices and supporting each other in their professional growth (Vangrieken et al., 2017).

The alignment between teachers' personal goals and the mission of the school further enhances their motivation and effectiveness. When teachers perceive their work as meaningful and aligned with their values, they are more likely to invest in their professional responsibilities and strive for excellence (Johnson & Blackwell, 2020). This sense of purpose and direction is crucial for sustaining long-term motivation and effectiveness, as it provides teachers with a clear vision of the impact they want to make in their students' lives (Freire, 2021).

The relationship between motivation and effectiveness also extends to teachers' ability to engage with parents and the wider school community. Motivated teachers recognize the importance of building strong relationships with parents and involving them in their children's education, which enhances student support and academic outcomes (Marzano, 2019). Effective communication and collaboration with parents are key components of teacher effectiveness, and motivated teachers are more likely to initiate and maintain these positive relationships (Smith & Gorard, 2020).

There is a significant connection between a teacher's motivation and their effectiveness, particularly in engaging with parents and the broader school community, motivated teachers understand the crucial role that strong relationships with parents play in enhancing student support and academic success. This understanding drives them to actively seek out and foster these relationships. Teachers who are motivated are more inclined to communicate and collaborate effectively with parents, recognizing that such partnerships can lead to improved educational outcomes for students.

Consequently, the effectiveness of teachers is partly dependent on their motivation to build and sustain these positive interactions, as supported by research findings from Marzano (2019) also Smith and Gorard (2020). This inference suggests that increasing teacher motivation could lead to better parent-teacher relationships, ultimately benefiting student achievement.

Table 27
Relationship Between Teacher Self-Efficacy and Teacher Effectiveness

Instruction	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Subject Matter Knowledge	.690**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies Assessment	.695**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.685**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.681**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.668**	0.000	Highly Significant
Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.681**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies Assessment	.670**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.631**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.610**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.600**	0.000	Highly Significant
Motivate Students			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.652**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies Assessment	.679**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.662**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.645**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.610**	0.000	Highly Significant
Maintain Discipline			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.634**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies Assessment	.637**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.642**	0.000	Highly Significant

Learning Environment	.635**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.545**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.687**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.698**	0.000	Highly Significant
Assessment	.642**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.641**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.631**	0.000	Highly Significant
Cope With Change			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.678**	0.000	Highly Significant
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.676**	0.000	Highly Significant
Assessment	.602**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learning Environment	.589**	0.000	Highly Significant
Effective Communication	.631**	0.000	Highly Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.01

Table 27 presents the association between teacher self-efficacy and teacher effectiveness. The computed r-values indicate a strong direct correlation and the resulting p-values were less than the alpha level. This means that a significant relationship exists and implies that the better the teacher's self-efficacy, the more effective the teachers are.

Teacher self-efficacy is highly significant in influencing teacher effectiveness in instructional practices. According to studies such as those referenced by Marzano (2019), teacher self-efficacy is highly significant in shaping how teachers plan, implement, and adapt their instructional strategies to meet student needs effectively. Teachers with high self-efficacy beliefs demonstrate greater confidence in their ability to manage classroom dynamics, engage students in learning, and facilitate academic growth.

Teacher self-efficacy plays a highly significant role in adapting instruction to individual student needs. According to Henson et al. (2019), teachers with higher levels of self-efficacy are more likely to employ flexible instructional strategies that cater to diverse student abilities and learning preferences.

Teacher self-efficacy is highly significant in motivating students. A longitudinal study by Jansen et al. (2021) highlights that teacher self-efficacy predicts students' academic motivation and achievement over time. Teachers who perceive themselves as effective in influencing student outcomes are more likely to maintain high expectations for all students, regardless of their backgrounds or prior academic performance. This consistency in belief and practice contributes to a motivational climate where students feel empowered to overcome challenges and strive for success.

Teacher self-efficacy plays a crucial role in promoting collaboration with colleagues and parents, as it is linked to effective communication and relationship-building skills. Educators who have confidence in their abilities to engage parents successfully foster trust, respond to concerns, and develop partnerships that enhance student learning and well-being. This positive relationship between teachers and parents creates a supportive home-school connection, which ultimately leads to improved educational outcomes for students.

More so, teacher self-efficacy is highly significant in coping with change. Harris and Jones (2021) discussed how teacher self-efficacy influences educators' ability to adapt to changes in educational policies and practices. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more resilient and proactive in embracing new teaching methodologies, technologies, or curriculum revisions. Their belief in their ability to navigate change fosters a positive attitude towards innovation and continuous improvement, mitigating resistance and promoting a culture of adaptability within schools.

The relationship between teacher self-efficacy and teacher effectiveness is highly significant and has profound implications for educational outcomes. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to implement innovative teaching strategies, maintain high expectations for all students, and persist in the face of challenges, all of which contribute to greater effectiveness in the classroom (Klassen & Tze, 2019). This confidence enables teachers to create a positive and inclusive learning environment where students feel supported and motivated to succeed.

Furthermore, teachers with high self-efficacy are more resilient and adaptable, qualities that are essential for effective teaching. Research has shown that self-efficacy is a strong predictor of teacher effectiveness across various contexts and educational levels. The impact of self-efficacy on teacher effectiveness is also evident in the way teachers approach assessment and feedback. The supportive role of school leadership and collegial collaboration in enhancing teacher self-efficacy and effectiveness cannot be overstated. The relationship between self-efficacy and effectiveness is also influenced by the alignment of teachers' personal goals with the goals of the school.

Table 28
Proposed Professional Development Program

Key Result Areas (KRAs)	Strategies/ Activities	Success Indicator	Person/ Office Responsible
<p>Work Tasks Motivation in terms of Class Preparation <i>Objectives: To re-capacitate teachers with strategies and techniques in approaching classroom routines and incidences</i> Teacher Effectiveness in terms of Subject Matter Knowledge <i>Objectives: To empower teachers in using contextualized, indigenize, and localized instructional materials to use school and community resources to help students.</i> Teacher Effectiveness in terms of Instructional Planning and Strategies <i>-To capacitate teachers in using student learning data, such as pre and post test results, student demographics,</i></p>	<p>From Planning to Teaching: Instructional Planning and Classroom Management Seminar-Training</p> <p>In this activity, trainings and seminars will be administered to re-capacitate teachers on methods and rigors of instructional planning and classroom management. Proposed contents are, but not limited to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Instructional decision-making during classes 2. Incidental teaching 3. Positive discipline in everyday teaching (PDET) 4. Contextualizing teaching and instructional materials 5. Community-based teaching 6. Utilizing and maximizing the use of student 	<p>90% of the teachers will be able to produce the following outputs: -contextualized instructional materials (community-based) -processed student data (considering privacy policies) -established classroom routine (documented)</p>	<p>Proponent Resource Person Training and development section of SDO Lipa City Participants Principals and SDO Key Personnel</p>

<p><i>anecdotal records, etc., for interventions and supplementary learning provisions</i></p> <p>Teacher Effectiveness in terms of Learning Environment</p> <p><i>-To revisit the establishment of classroom routine in maintaining a classroom setting that minimizes disruption.</i></p>	<p>data</p> <p>7. Establishing classroom routine across all levels</p> <p>8. Contextualization, localization, and indigenization</p> <p>9. Research-based Intervention Programs and supplemental activities.</p>		
<p>Work Tasks Motivation in terms of Teaching</p> <p><i>-To survey the availability of teaching and learning materials for teacher's and students' use</i></p> <p>Teacher's Self-Efficacy in terms of Instruction</p> <p><i>-To produce relevant thematic explanations and connections of lessons to be presented to the students in the beginning of lessons</i></p> <p>Teacher's Self-Efficacy in terms of Adapt Instruction to Individual Needs</p> <p><i>-To re-introduce differentiated instructions (DI) and multiple intelligences (MI) in</i></p>	<p>Recapitulating Teachers of 21st Century Teaching Methods in Teaching 21st Century Learners</p> <p>Lecture, demonstration, and return demonstration are the strategies suggested to address clustered KRAs on teaching and learning. Proposed contents are, but not limited to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unpacking and dissecting of learning competencies for teaching 2. Packaging lessons for all levels of learners 3. Re-introduction of teaching approaches, 	<p>85%-90% of the participants will be able to produce the following outputs at the end of the training:</p> <p>-budget of work for at least 1 quarter</p> <p>-matrix of lessons indicating teaching, learning, thematic topics, and assessment strategies</p> <p>-teaching methods, strategies, and techniques bank”</p>	<p>Proponent Resource Person Training and development section of SDO Lipa City Participants Principals and SDO Key Personnel</p>

<p><i>teaching standardized classrooms to provide realistic challenge for all students even in mixed ability classes</i></p> <p>Teacher's Self-Efficacy in terms of Cope With Change</p> <p><i>-To revisit prominent schools of thoughts and prominent pedagogies (2C-2I-1R) that are being used in DEPED to rationalize the use of any instructional method that the school and department decides to use</i></p>	<p>methods, and strategies side by side with concrete examples across all learning areas. This training/seminar should also concretize these strategies vis-à-vis learning objectives or competencies, the corresponding lesson development, assessment, grading/rubric, instructional materials, and the like.</p> <p>4. Providing participants with usable "teaching methods, strategies, and techniques bank" across all disciplines and levels</p>		
<p>Teacher's Self-Efficacy in terms of Motivating Students</p> <p><i>-Re-introduction of the use of criterion-based rubrics in assessing learning outcomes to present learners with achievable</i></p>	<p>Discipline, Motivation, and Learning in the 21st Century Classroom</p> <p>In this area, the following are the proposed contents, but are not limited to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Seminar on student 	<p>90-95% the participant in the training are expected to produce:</p> <p>-anonymous list of student with corresponding disruptive or deviant behavior (may be</p>	<p>Proponent Resource Person Training and development section of SDO Lipa City Participants Principals and SDO Key Personnel</p>

<p><i>goals to awaken the desire to learn even among the lowest achieving students</i></p> <p>Teacher's Self-Efficacy in terms of Maintaining Discipline <i>-To utilize positive discipline in everyday teaching (PDET) and Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) techniques in maintaining classroom discipline; in controlling even the most aggressive students</i></p>	<p>motivation and behavior</p> <p>2. Case study analysis presentation of varied learner behaviors and aptitudes.</p> <p>3. Both psychological first aid capacity training for teachers</p> <p>4. "What to do" seminars for varied classroom scenarios that involve motivation and behavior</p> <p>5. Teacher empowerment of (PDET) and (SEL)</p>	<p>collaborative across levels, if teachers are dealing with same set of students) -intervention plan for the student (utilizing SEL and PDET techniques)</p>	
<p>Work Tasks Motivation in terms of Evaluation of students <i>-To revisit assessment and evaluation methods, strategies, and techniques</i></p> <p>Teacher Effectiveness in terms of Assessment <i>-To empower teachers in setting up SMART objectives to facilitate revising contents to</i></p>	<p>Assessment and Evaluation in the 21st Century Educational Landscape</p> <p>To re-capacitate the participants in terms of assessment and evaluation, the following topics and/or activities are proposed:</p> <p>1. An inventory of assessment and evaluation methods and where to use them— participants</p>	<p>85%-90% of the participants are expected to produce: - budget of work for at least 1 quarter and matrix of lessons indicating teaching, learning, and assessment strategies (continuation or in collaboration with the training on teaching and learning -assessment and evaluation strategy bank</p>	<p>Proponent Resource Person Training and development section of SDO Lipa City Participants Principals and SDO Key Personnel</p>

<p><i>enhance students' achievement</i></p>	<p>will be re—introduced with the mentioned topic. More so, they will be presented with specific instructional scenario wherein assessment strategies are used for an identified learning objective or competency</p> <p>2. Revisiting assessment for learning, assessment of learning, and assessment as learning</p>		
<p>Work Tasks Motivation in terms of Administrative Tasks <i>-To revisit teachers' responsibilities and privileges, including participating in teachers and employees' union and association</i></p> <p>Work Tasks Motivation in terms of Complementary Tasks <i>-to clarify and reiterate scope of work and tasks and responsibilities</i></p>	<p>Quasi-Assignments, Administrative Tasks, and Professionalization: A Revisit</p> <p>In light with DEPED Order 002, s. 2024, administrative tasks for teachers are removed, and thus specified in the memo are a roster of specific and existing duties and responsibilities that should be lifted from the teacher's tasks. Despite of this, there are still remaining quasi-</p>	<p>95%-100% of the participants are expected to produce:</p> <p>-roster of localized remaining quasi-assignment and administrative tasks for teachers as juxtaposed to the DEPED calendar (including timeline)</p>	<p>Proponent Resource Person Training and development section of SDO Lipa City Participants Principals and SDO Key Personnel</p>

<p><i>stipulated in position description forms (PDF) for each career stage, including but not limited to accreditation and audit tasks, etc.</i></p>	<p>assignments that are being performed by teachers in relation to professionalization and other administrative roles. Topics regarding this matter are suggested, but not limited to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Orientation on the remaining administrative related tasks and quasi assignments 2. Inventory of these tasks, specific timeline, and persons concerned as juxtaposed with DEPED calendar to let teachers prepare and schedule activities beforehand <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Accreditations (visits for SBM, etc.) b. Contests and specific dates c. Trainings and seminars with specific dates to help them for instructional planning and adjustments 		
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<p>Teacher's Self-Efficacy in terms of Cooperate With Colleagues and Parents</p> <p><i>-To empower teachers with interpersonal skills and conflict resolution management</i></p> <p>Teacher Effectiveness in terms of Effective Communication</p> <p><i>-To re-capacitate teachers in communicating in the workplace, through various media and forms, through the use of correct vocabulary and grammar in speaking & writing.</i></p>	<p>Seminar on Interpersonal Relations and Communication in the Workplace</p> <p>Related to this topic are the activities pertaining to the maintaining and uplifting of teacher professionalization and development of interpersonal relations. Topics such as below are suggested, but not limited to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Specific strategies on how to deal with partnerships for teaching and learning <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Partnership with parents b. With industry c. With academe d. With community e. With other teachers for collaboration 2. Technical writing for teachers 3. Conversational gambits and communicative English 	<p>90-95% of the participants in the training workshop are expected to produce the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -examples of technical documents related to teaching and learning -narrative reports -request letters of different styles -memo -incident report -anecdotal -and others, as applicable 	<p>Proponent Resource Person Training and development section of SDO Lipa City Participants Principals and SDO Key Personnel</p>
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	4. Conflict resolution		
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Table 28 in the preceding pages presents the professional development program that is proposed for the Basic Education Teachers in the Schools Division of Lipa City. The proposed program is divided into four columns, as indicated: Key Result Areas (KRAs), the corresponding strategies or activities, the success indicators, and the person or office responsible.

The proposed program is intended to be implemented in a staggered manner, across the whole fiscal year. This program will be strategically implemented into different legs. Each leg is named under six key activities, namely: 1.) Instructional Planning and Classroom Management, 2.) Teaching and Learning, 3. Discipline and Motivation, 4.) Assessment and Evaluation, 5.) Quasi-Assignments, Administrative Tasks, and Professionalization, and 6.) Interpersonal Relations and Communication. These activities are formulated to address the clustered issues and concerns that were drawn out from the results of this study, which are presented in the first column through the heading *key result areas (KRA)*.

The proposed professional development program for Basic Education Teachers is firmly rooted in the principles of work task motivation, teacher self-efficacy, and teacher effectiveness. By addressing key areas of instructional planning, classroom management, teaching and learning, discipline and motivation, assessment and evaluation, quasi-assignments, administrative tasks, professionalization, and interpersonal relations and communication, the program provides a comprehensive approach to professional development. This approach not only enhances teachers' motivation and self-efficacy but also significantly improves their effectiveness in the classroom, leading to better educational outcomes for students.

Research has consistently demonstrated that well-structured professional development programs that align with these core principles significantly enhance teachers' instructional practices and overall effectiveness in the classroom (Desimone & Garet, 2015).

Instructional Planning and Classroom Management are critical components of effective teaching. Teachers who are well-prepared and possess strong classroom management skills are better able to create conducive learning environments that promote student engagement and achievement (Marzano, 2019). This aspect of the program directly taps into teachers' work task motivation by providing them with practical strategies and tools to plan and manage their classrooms efficiently, thereby enhancing

their self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997). When teachers feel competent in their ability to plan and manage their classrooms, their confidence increases, leading to more effective teaching practices.

The Teaching and Learning component focuses on equipping teachers with innovative instructional strategies that cater to diverse learning needs. Discipline and Motivation are pivotal in maintaining a positive and productive classroom environment. This component of the program addresses the motivational aspects of teaching, helping teachers to develop strategies that enhance student motivation and engagement. By building their skills in discipline and motivation, teachers' self-efficacy is reinforced, as they feel more capable of handling classroom challenges and promoting positive student behavior (Klassen & Tze, 2019).

Assessment and Evaluation are essential for monitoring student progress and informing instructional decisions. This aspect of the program enhances teachers' self-efficacy by equipping them with the skills to conduct accurate assessments and use data to improve their teaching practices. When teachers are confident in their ability to assess and evaluate student performance, their overall effectiveness in the classroom is significantly enhanced (Hattie, 2009).

The inclusion of Quasi-Assignments, Administrative Tasks, and Professionalization in the program acknowledges the multifaceted nature of the teaching profession. This component of the program helps teachers develop the necessary skills to manage these tasks efficiently, thereby reducing job-related stress and enhancing their motivation.

Interpersonal Relations and Communication are fundamental to building a collaborative and supportive school environment. Effective communication skills are essential for fostering positive relationships with students, colleagues, and parents (Van den Borre et al., 2020). This component of the program focuses on enhancing teachers' interpersonal skills, which are critical for creating a positive school culture and promoting collaborative practices. Teachers who are skilled in communication are more likely to build strong relationships, receive support from their peers, and engage in collaborative problem-solving, all of which contribute to their self-efficacy and effectiveness (Johnson & Blackwell, 2020). By addressing key areas of teaching practice and providing opportunities for professional growth, the program fosters intrinsic motivation among teachers, encouraging them to strive for excellence in their work. Extrinsic motivators, such as recognition and career advancement, are also incorporated to reinforce teachers' efforts and enhance their commitment to their professional responsibilities (Marzano, 2019).

Each component of the program is designed to build teachers' confidence in their skills and abilities, thereby enhancing their self-efficacy. Teacher effectiveness, which refers to the impact of teachers' practices on student learning and achievement, is the ultimate goal of the professional development program. Effective teachers are those who

can create positive learning environments, engage students in meaningful learning experiences, and foster academic success.

Conclusions

The following were concluded from the results of this study:

1. The respondents were predominantly female with Master's degree, who teach in the elementary school and have 10 years and below teaching experience.
2. In terms of work tasks motivations, the respondents corresponded completely to performing responsibilities as regards class preparation, teaching, evaluation of students, administrative tasks, and complimentary tasks.
3. The respondents deemed they were always self-efficacious or confident in performing teaching-related duties in connection to instruction, adapting instruction to individual needs, motivating students, maintaining discipline, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with change.
4. The respondents perceived they were always effective in performing duties as related to subject matter knowledge, assessment, learning environment, and effective communication.
5. In terms of work task motivation, indicators on assessments on teaching, evaluation of students, and complementary tasks differed according to sex. On the other hand, assessments on class preparation and complementary tasks varied according to their years of teaching experience. When it comes to identifying self-efficacy, components on assessments on instruction, adapting to individual needs, motivating students, maintaining discipline, and cooperating with colleagues and parents varied when the respondents were grouped according to sex. Meanwhile, assessments on coping with change differed according to years of teaching experience. Finally, when respondents were grouped according to sex, teacher effectiveness was assessed differently in the aspects of subject matter knowledge, assessment, learning environment, and effective communication.
6. Highly significant relationships exist between work task motivation and teacher self-efficacy, work task motivation and teacher effectiveness, and teacher self-efficacy and teacher effectiveness. This could imply that teachers who are more motivated by their work tasks tend to have higher self-efficacy. Moreover, higher levels of motivation in work tasks are associated with greater teacher effectiveness. Finally teachers with higher self-efficacy tend to be more effective in their teaching.
7. A professional development program for the Basic Education Teachers in the Schools Division of Lipa City based on the assessments, significant differences, and significant relationships of the variables of the study was proposed.

Recommendations

1. DEPED may look into the results of this study to consider how work tasks motivation, self-efficacy, and effectiveness of teachers relate, correspond, and interact with each other to further associate them with teachers' welfare,

capacities, performance, and efficiency. This could be beneficial in implementing programs and policies for the wellbeing of teachers and the performance of their duties.

2. DEPED Lipa City may utilize and/or adopt the professional development program that is proposed for the Basic Education Teachers in the Schools Division of Lipa City.
3. School administrators may look into the result of this study and take into consideration work task motivations, efficacy, and effectiveness in planning for professional development of teachers and taking it into account in the school implementation plans, procurement plans, and other related matters.
4. K-12 teachers may refer to the findings of this research as regards motivation for work tasks, efficacy, and effectiveness to try to understand the effects of these indicators to their performance. More so, they can use the suggestions in the action plan to further improve their performance in terms of the mentioned indicators.
5. The Professional Development Program for K-12 teachers may be tabled for discussion, implementation and further evaluation.
6. Future researchers may investigate the significant differences in the respondents' assessments of the three variables when the participants were grouped according to different profile variables. More so, these variables can be investigated as to their mediating effect, significant effect, moderating effect, etc.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This declaration affirms that the author has adhered to ethical research practices in conducting the study. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, ensuring they were fully aware of their participation and had the freedom to withdraw at any time without consequence. Anonymity was rigorously maintained to protect the identities of participants, and their well-being was prioritized throughout the research process. There are no conflicts of interest associated with this study, and strict measures were taken to avoid plagiarism. Furthermore, the interpretation of findings was conducted without bias, and the results are solely intended for research purposes, reflecting a commitment to integrity and ethical standards in academic inquiry.

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